

ACCOUNTING INFORMATION AND MARKET VALUE OF QUOTED MANUFACTURING COMPANIES IN NIGERIA: DERIVED DATA APPROACH

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<p>Keyword: ¹Accounting Information [Net Assets Per Share (NAPS)], ²Market Value and ³Quoted Manufacturing Companies</p>	<p>Abstract: The study was conducted to examine the influence of accounting information on market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Items of transactions reported on financial statements are expected to influence shareholders' wealth positively through improvement in share price of quoted companies. It seems that this does not hold in quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. This necessitated the conduct of this study. Ex-post facto design was employed in the study because it required secondary data. Accounting Information (independent variable) was represented by Net Assets Per Share (NAPS). The dependent variable, Market Value (MV) was represented by share price (SP) while Asset Turnover Ratio (ATR) was chosen as a control variable for the study. The population of the study was Thirty-one (31) manufacturing companies whose shares were traded on Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) based on the financial year of these companies. Twenty-Three (23) companies were selected as sample size for the study on the basis of availability of published financial statements. Data required were collected from the sampled companies from 2013 to 2024. The nature of data was panel data. Descriptive statistics and pooled panel linear regression statistical tools were used to analyze the data collected. The result of the analysis revealed that NAPS had positive and significant influence on MV of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. From the findings, the researcher concluded that accounting information had a positive and significant influence on market value of quoted manufacturing companies in</p>
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Nigeria. It was recommended that the managers of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria should raise net assets per share by acquiring more of non-current assets to improve upon the market value of the entities.

1. Introduction

The numerous factors are capable of assisting investors/management to make decisions at any time in accordance with the published financial statements often made available at the end of an accounting period (Enofe *et al.*, 2014). These factors could be regarded as attributes of accounting information because they are presented on financial statements. In contemporary time, accounting information is crucial to managers and other users of financial statements because the expectation of any kind of investment is to maximize returns. Accounting information affects all aspects of organization because it involves the utilization of available resources with the expectation of generating maximum returns or profits.

Accounting information is described as information presented on published financial statements of quoted companies in different accounting periods (Davies and Macfubara, 2018). The variables that represent accounting information of quoted companies are capable of influencing market value of the entities at any time depending on the level of performance or effectiveness of strategies and policies implemented by the managers/directors (Kousenidis *et al.*, 2012). The key variables of

accounting information are net assets per share (NAPS) and earnings per share (EPS) and the one considered in this study is net assets per share (NAPS) because it is rarely used in previous the studies.

Net assets per share is described as the difference between total assets and current liabilities of a company divided by equity shares outstanding (Olaniyi *et al.*, 2022). The influence of all the attributes of accounting information on market value of quoted companies might either be positively or negatively felt depending on the operations carried out from which the outcomes are reported on financial statements. Market value is described as the level of improvement in the indicators of shareholders' wealth which include share price, market capitalization, and market value of equity and price earnings ratio. The various indicators of market value are often influenced by the book value items reported on financial statements. Thus, the influence of accounting information on market value of quoted companies could be established empirically. Because of the importance of accounting information often prepared and presented on financial statements of quoted companies by managers/directors, the assessment of the influence of the variable of

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accounting information on market value of quoted companies becomes an interesting area of research.

Accounting information and market value of quoted entities is an interesting area of research that cuts across various aspects of elements of financial statements. Accounting information is one of the reasons behind the growth of quoted companies in different countries of the world. Several studies in this area of interest have been conducted with the use of variables such as earnings per share, dividend per share and price earnings ratio to represent accounting information (Shamki, 2012; Irsath *et al.*, 2015; Rahman and Liu, 2021). The use of indicator like net assets per share to represent accounting information in empirical studies are limited in the literature. The empirical results of these studies have mixed results depending on the sectors used and the time frame selected for the studies. In most of the previous studies conducted, the selection of the time frame where significant changes have taken place on the published financial statements were not taken into consideration and this could be seen as one reason of the conflicting empirical results obtained in those studies.

The post-adoption period of international financial reporting standards (IFRSs) is considered in this study. Quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria, which consist of quoted consumer and industrial goods entities, have limited studies especially with the use of variable

like net assets per share to establish the influence on share price. The connection between the attributes of financial statements and factors of market value is usually expected because the efficiency of managers is reflected on the reported items of transactions on financial statements, and they are expected to influence market value as well. Thus, an attribute of accounting information is expected to influence the share price of a company either positively or negatively because the level of performance achieved by managers is expected to have significant connection with the variables of shareholders' wealth.

The accounting information often provided on the published financial reports of quoted companies is expected to be utilized effectively by managers to improve upon the performance of future operation by ensuring that the occurrence of previous adverse outcomes does not repeat. By so doing, positive and significant influence of the variables of accounting information on market value is expected to be achieved. Accounting information is also expected to direct managers on the pattern of investments on assets considering the level of profits made over the years. From the published financial statements of selected quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria, it seems that accounting information provided by financial statements of previous accounting years is not adequately put into action by managers to improve upon their operations and

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thus, adverse outcomes are achieved to the point that investments on more assets are made while earnings and other performance indicators are declining (see appendix iv). It is on this note that the researcher is in doubt whether the variable of accounting information, which is net assets per share, influence upon the market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria from 2013 to 2024. The main objective of the study was to investigate the influence of net assets per share on share price of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

2. Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Accounting Information

Accounting information is described as critical information for managerial decision in quoted companies as well as other stakeholders. This is because of the roles played by accounting in business organizations for the purpose of providing accurate records about the past events that are critical for decision to be made, for correction of deviation and improvement in the wealth of shareholders (Sukmadilaga *et al.*, 2023). When talking about accounting information, there are two critical terms to be considered which are accounting and information. Accounting is perceived to be the systematic process of recording historical events expressed in monetary terms for the purpose of providing useful information that could guide the continuous operation of the organization (Vijitha and Nimalathan, 2014; Abazu and

Onuora, 2023; Závodný and Procházka, 2023). The provision of historical data about various transactions of quoted companies is made possible through accounting. On this note, it could be said that accounting is aimed at providing information for various users which are broadly classified into internal and external users (Kousenidis *et al.*, 2012). In other words, one could describe accounting as information generating mechanism or activities performed by set of individuals that have been trained in the field professionally to record, analyse and interpret transactions (Irsath *et al.*, 2015).

Accounting is also described as the systematic process of collecting, recording, classifying, interpreting financial data to arrive at useful information for the managers and other users of accounting information for decision purposes (Rahman and Liu, 2021). In all the definitions of accounting, the ultimate expectation is always to arrive at information for sound decision to be made in an organization. Thus, accounting is seen as a lifeblood of modern organizations because without proper and accurate records maintained in an organization, future operation of such organization might not be assured. The going concern status of any organization solely rely on the effectiveness of the recording processes maintained in an organization which incorporates the internal control system (Shehzad and Ismail, 2014). This simply means that in an organization where professional and experienced accountants are not involved, the

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going concern status of such company might be threatened as the information generated by accounting activities is so crucial for future decision-making and for the assurance of continuous operation of the company. When talking about accounting in this situation, the various items reported on the financial statements are critical factors that help to provide information to managers and other stakeholders of organization.

Also, the various aspects or types of accounting are all critical in different organization because the items of transaction presented financial statements are classified as basis for deriving information. Information on the other hand is described as the processed data that could be used to solve problems or to correct deviant results in future (Shamki, 2012; Eugenio *et al.*, 2019). Information is derived as a result of collection of data as well as processing them. The processes of publishing financial statements of quoted companies are similar to data processing procedures which has to do with collection of transaction, recording, classifying and interpreting for the purpose of deriving information (Hassan and Haque, 2017). When talking about information in accounting perspective, it is simply regarded as the information presented on general-purpose financial statements published by quoted companies.

2.1.2 Net Assets per Share

Net assets per share is a fundamental factor of accounting information that usually represents the extent to which managers of quoted companies have invested the available funds sourced from both debt and equity to grow the firms for the owners divided by equity shares outstanding (Al-Slehat, 2020). Net assets are often computed as the difference between total assets less current liabilities in an accounting period for a quoted company (Anuar *et al.*, 2021). The key determinants of the magnitude of net assets are the level of total assets and current liabilities in an accounting period. For appropriate understanding of net assets per share, it is crucial to explain the meaning of asset in an accounting. Asset has been defined by the conceptual framework of international accounting standard board (IASB) for developing international financial reporting standards (IFRSs) as the resource controlled by an entity from which future economic benefits are expected to flow into the company.

Assets are defined as those valuable properties or item of transactions owned and controlled by a company and used for the conduct of daily business activities (Ariyani *et al.*, 2018). In accordance with the perception of international accounting standards, an item of transaction is recognised as an asset when the cost incurred on the asset could be measured reliably and there is possibility that the asset is capable of generating future economic benefits into the entity. As a quoted company continues to use an asset,

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essential things to consider about the asset are depreciation, impairment and the importance of the asset. Assets are broadly classified into non-current assets and current assets (Setiadharm and Machali, 2017; Shamki and Al-Hamashi, 2024). The aggregation of the two classifications of assets is regarded as total assets. Non-current assets are resource controlled by entity with the attributes such as tangible and intangible in nature, require huge amount in acquisition and are expected to be used for the generation of revenue in more than one accounting period (Ariyani *et al.*, 2018).

Thus, non-current assets could be described as those assets that could be seen and unseen, that could be used in more than one accounting period as well as requiring huge amount of funds to acquire (Charlie and Edet, 2023). On the other hand, and as the name implies, current assets are the aggregate of items of transaction that are often used within one accounting period in piloting the activities of a company. The major items that constitute current assets of a quoted company are inventories, account receivables, cash and other marketable securities (Anuar, *et al.*, 2021). As stated earlier, the key attributes that determine the level of net assets are total assets and current liabilities. This simply means that when current liabilities are larger than current assets in accounting period, it therefore means that the magnitude of net assets will be small and when current liabilities is less than current assets in an accounting period, it means

that the net assets will be large as portion of current assets less current liabilities will be added to non-current asset in such situation (Al-Slehat, 2020).

When total assets are made up of a greater proportion of non-current assets and current assets are greater than current liabilities in an accounting period, the magnitude of net assets in such situation will be large and when the composition of total assets has a less proportion of non-current assets where current assets are less than current liabilities, the magnitude of net assets will be lower (Buzinskiene and Rudyte, 2021). In a generic situation, when net assets is large, it could be said that the managers of such company are more concerned in utilizing less or minimal current liabilities or short-term debt in carrying out the operations of the entity (Harvest *et al.*, 2022). On the other hand, when net assets are minimal, it could be said that the managers of such firm have accumulated less non-current asset and more of current liabilities greater than current assets in the accounting period (Charlie and Edet, 2023). Larger net assets are capable of attracting the interest of potential investors because it could be viewed as a company that has less short-term financial obligations and with the larger asset portfolio, the reputation of the company in the market is assured.

Net assets per share is an accounting ratio that represents the value of assets attributed to a unit of shares of a quoted company in an accounting period (Anuar *et al.*, 2021). It is calculated as the

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value of total assets minus current liabilities divided by equity shares outstanding in an accounting period (Bartha *et al.*, 2022). The determinants of net assets per share are total assets, current liabilities and equity shares outstanding. This simply means that the magnitude of net assets per share is highly defined by the value of total assets, total current liabilities and equity shares in an accounting period. When total assets in an accounting period are large with minimal current liabilities and equity shares, the value of net assets per share will be large and when the total assets of a quoted company are minimal with larger current liabilities and equity shares, the value of net assets per share will be lower. Also, when total assets are large with minimal current liabilities with a larger value of equity shares outstanding, net assets per share will be lower especially when equity shares outstanding is greater than the net assets (Boonyanet and Promsen, 2024).

Based on this analogy, it could be said that net assets per share is an essential variable of accounting information that could influence the share price of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

2.1.3 Market Value

Market value is described as the level of improvement in shareholders' value. There are several indicators that could represent market value of quoted companies recognised by scholars and researchers in the field of accounting and finance. In assessing the market

value of an entity, combination of some of these indicators is usually recommended because one particular indicator might point out information that is in conflict with another indicator (Buzinskiene and Rudyte, 2021). In many occasions, to assess the ideal market value of a quoted company when several indicators are put together, interpretation is usually based on the different indicators used and one might not really generalise that the market value of a company has really improved or decline drastically (Altahtamouni, 2018). Some of the factors that could represent market value include share price, Tobin's Q, market capitalization, market value of equity and price earnings ratio. Share price is a measure of market value in this study and it is discussed appropriately.

Share price is described as the current market price of shares of a quoted company at a given period. It is the rate of exchange that indicate the worth of shares outstanding for all the equity shareholders (Ni *et al.*, 2019). Stock price is an indicator that indicates how well a company is doing to maximise the wealth of the shareholders (Kraipornsak and Poramapojn, 2021). Often times, stock price is seen as a representative of the outcomes of the internal operation of an organization through the effective strategic formulation of the management (Itan and Riana, 2021). This is why in some cases the efficiency and effectiveness of managers of quoted entities is represented by the level of stock price (Shehzad and Ismail, 2014). When the stock

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price is low, it might be described as the inefficiency or ineffectiveness of the strategy formulated and implemented by the directors for the fact that directors are seen as agents of quoted companies entrusted with the responsibility of ensuring that the wealth of the owners is maximized. When the stock price is high, managers of quoted entities are usually applauded because of the level of performance attained through the improvement in the stock price.

In other words, it is often seen as a situation whereby the strategies formulated and implemented and policies made by the managers have yielded optimal results to the owners. Stock price is usually considered as a single indicator that might represent market value of a quoted company as well as firm value (Altahtamouni, 2018). It is also used to represent shareholders' wealth creation or shareholders' wealth maximization (Shamki, 2012). Stock prices are of different types usually presented statistically in a stock market bulletin and these include opening stock price, closing stock price, high stock price, low price and adjusted closing stock price. Opening stock price is described as the stock price quoted by a stock exchange for a share of a company at the beginning of a period which might be a day, a week, a month and a year (Rahman and Liu, 2021). Closing stock price is the shared price quoted by a stock market for an entity at the end of operation which might be a day, a week, a month or a year (Ni *et al.*, 2019).

The high of stock price is described as the maximum share price for a stock of a company in a certain period and the low of stock price is the minimum share price quoted by a stock market for the unit of share of a firm at a given period (Ha and Minh, 2020; Kraipornsak and Poramapojn, 2021). The adjusted closing price is the stock price quoted by a stock market for a company at the end of an accounting period after adjusting for all errors. In several empirical studies, the adjusted closing price is often utilized as an indicator of market value, firm value, shareholders' wealth maximization and so on (Altahtamouni, 2018). Stock price of a company is often quoted daily, weekly, monthly and yearly. It is often important to state that stock price of any quoted company is influenced by several factors both quantitative and qualitative factors, firm-based factors and macroeconomic factors (Buzinskiene and Rudyte, 2021). In this study, the focus is on firm-based factors regarded as accounting information represented by attributes such as net assets per share. Thus, closing price of shares is used as a proxy for market value in this study.

2.1.4 Assets Turnover Ratio

The efficiency of managers in utilizing the accumulated assets to generate more revenue is regarded as assets turnover ratio. Thus, the efficacy of revenue generated by a quoted company in any accounting period could be represented by assets turnover ratio. Assets turnover ratio is described as revenue divided by

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total assets in an accounting period (Khanna, 2014). Total revenue and assets are the key determinants of assets turnover ratio (Tarik, 2021). Revenue is described as the income made through the sales of products manufactured by a company. It could also be described as income generated in normal business operation of a quoted company (Irsath *et al.*, 2015). It could be used to calculate the efficiency of managers in utilizing the assets accumulated.

In every accounting period, managers of quoted companies usually anticipate larger revenue to be realised and this is why meaningful policies are formulated from the implemented strategies to improve upon the revenue. In the activities of quoted companies, what constitutes revenue is simply regarded as the income generated from the principal activities of the entities such as the sales of products manufactured by the companies or income from services rendered by the entities to individuals or other corporate entities (Rahman and Liu, 2021). The process in which revenue could influence earnings either positively or negatively depends on how much revenue is made in an accounting period as well as the techniques of cost and expenses management adopted by the managers (Shehzad and Ismail, 2014). Assets are regarded as resource controlled by a quoted company from which future economic benefits are expected to flow into the firm.

Assets turnover ratio is an efficiency ratio that shows how the accumulated assets are utilised to

generate revenue in a quoted company. It is calculated as total revenue generated in an accounting period divided by total assets. Assets turnover ratio is basically used for financial analysis and valuation of company status, management performance evaluation and for investment decision (Uwuigbe *et al.*, 2016). Thus, the influence of this attribute on market value is essential, precisely, in this study.

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Signalling Theory

Signalling theory was formulated and advanced by Spence in 1973 based on his observation on some attributes which he believed to provide signals for essential information. Based on the perspective of the author, certain attributes are indicators that could help to provide information for effective decision making and it is always expected that the parameters or indicators are provided at any time before decision is taken. The author of the theory also made it clear that it is important to understand different signals for decision making at any time. This is because there could be different signals pointing at different information which means that adequate understanding of such signals might help in effective decision making. Financial statements usually prepared and published by managers/directors of quoted companies are always with several items of transactions that are regarded as sources of information to the investors or stakeholders. The classification of various components of financial statements into

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the respective elements such as revenue, expenses, assets, equity and liabilities could also help to provide information for decision making at any time.

According to Spence (1973), the magnitude of items of transactions presented at the end of an accounting period for a quoted company might be a signal to vital information. This simply means that signalling theory is related to accounting information as the various items of transactions reported on financial statements like net assets per share is a signal of essential information to investors which could also influence the wealth of the shareholders or market value of the entity. Larger net assets reported at the end of accounting period for a quoted company in different accounting period with greater proportion of non-current assets indicates that the entity is a large firm which will always generate adequate revenue and maximize the wealth of the shareholders (Etim *et al.*, 2022). With the large net assets base recorded by a quoted entity in different accounting period investors (both potential) will classify such firm as one that will always report larger revenue, profit, total equity as well as paying larger amount of dividends to the shareholders at the end of every accounting period. Such company will always provide information to the debt holders in terms of paying back the interest of the debts annually and the principal at maturity.

Larger profit made by a quoted entity in different accounting periods shows that such company is

doing well especially when the greater proportion such profit is real and not just paper profit where adequate cash is maintained by the company (Ogiriki and Stephen, 2022). Larger profit recorded by a quoted company in different accounting period with positive cash flow balance shows that the entity is progressing and the interest of the various stakeholders might be protected without any form of default. This simply means that a quoted entity with fluctuating profits in some years and losses is one that investors might be discouraged because it seems such entity might not be able to honour obligations as at when due because of inadequate cash caused by losses recorded from operation in different accounting periods (Purwaningrum and Adhikara, 2022).

Based on the discussion and in accordance with signalling theory, it could be said that the various attributes of accounting information are signals to investors and the magnitude of items of transactions reported at the end of operation are crucial factors that could influence the wealth of the shareholders either positively or negatively. In this case, net assets per share is a signal of accounting information that provides information to potential and existing investors which might also influence market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria either positively or negatively. The assertion in this study is that signalling theory is related as the performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria reported on financial

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statements annually is with signals for decision making which could in turn maximize the wealth of the shareholders in terms of improvement in share price and growth in other wealth maximization indicators. In this case, the theory was adopted in this study.

2.3 Empirical Review

Vijitha and Nimalathasan (2014) examined the value relevance of accounting information and share price: A study of listed manufacturing companies in Sri Lanka. The aim of the study was to showcase empirical evidence concerning value relevance of accounting information of manufacturing companies in Colombo Stock Exchange (CSE). The study covered the period from 2007 to 2011. The accounting information used in this study were earnings per share (EPS), net assets value per share (NAVPS) and return on equity (ROE). Also, price earnings ratio to share price to share price. Relevant data were sourced from the published annual reports and financial statements of the manufacturing firms listed in CSE in Sri Lanka. The data were analysed using multiple regression technique and the result showed that there was a significant impact of accounting information on the share price. The result also indicated a significant correlation between value relevance of accounting information and share price.

Okafor *et al.* (2017) conducted a study on IFRS adoption and the value relevance of accounting information in Nigeria: An empirical study. The intention of the researchers was to examine the

influence of International Financial Reporting Standards adoption on the value relevance of accounting information in Nigerian firms. The accounting information used in the study were Book Value (BV), Earnings per Share (EPS) and cash flow from operating consumer firms' sector in Nigeria. The population of the study was comprised of twenty-five (25) consumer firms whose shares were listed on the floor of Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) as at 31st December 2015. The period of the study covered 2008 to 2015. Relevant data were sourced from the published annual reports and financial statements of the firms chosen for the study. The sourced data were analysed using panel regression technique. The result of the analysis showed the adoption of IFRSs significantly influenced BV, EPS and cash flows from operating activities. Thus, EPS was shown to have been influenced most. From the findings of the study, it was recommended by the researchers that the values of earnings, book values of equity and cash flows from operating activities should be considered by investors in the annual reports and financial statements of firms prepared in accordance with the standard of IFRSs before making any investment decisions.

Kwon (2018) studied the value relevance of accounting information: Focusing on US and China. The intention of the researcher was to ascertain how accounting information affect the corporate value of manufacturing companies listed on US and Chinese stock markets. The

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period of the study was from 2008 to 2015. The accounting information being the independent variable was proxied by book value of equity (BVE), accounting earnings (AE), operating income (OI) and operating cash flow (OCF). Quantitative technique was employed in the study. Relevant data were obtained from the published annual reports and financial statements of the manufacturing firms. The data were analysed using regression technique. From the analysis, it was observed that book value of equity exerted a substantial influence on firm value. It was found that AE, OI and OCF had a negative influence on firm value. By comparing the results of regression analyses of US and Chinese manufacturing companies, it was observed that BVE was the most valuable factor among US companies; OCF exerted positive and material influence on firm value while AE and OI negatively influence firm value. For Chinese firms, accounting earnings had the highest value relevance, followed by operating income and net cash flows, while operating cash flow exerted a negative influence on firm value.

Tarik (2021) conducted a study on the value relevance of accounting information and its impact on stock prices: A study on listed pharmaceutical companies at Dhaka stock exchange of Bangladesh. The intention of the researcher was to assess the influence of value relevance of accounting information on pharmaceutical companies' share price at the Dhaka Stock Exchange (DSE) of Bangladesh. The

variables used for the study were EPS, net operating cash flow per share, net asset value per share, cash dividend per share, and stock dividend per share and market value per share. The period of the study covered 2017 to 2019. Relevant data in relative to the variables of the study were retrieved from the published annual reports and financial statements of the pharmaceutical companies in DSE sampled for the study. The obtained data were analysed using some analytical tools such as correlation, ANOVA and regression analysis. The results of the analysis ascertained that there was a statistical positive and significant relationship of net operating cash flow per share, net assets value per share with market value per share. On the other hand, showed that there was negative and significant influence of EPS on market value per share. The outcomes of the analysis also indicated that cash dividend per share and stock dividend per share had positive and inconsequential relationship with market value per share.

Cehade and Prochazka (2022) investigated value relevance of accounting information in an emerging market: The case of IFRS adoption by non-financial listed firms in Saudi Arabia. The study aimed at examining value relevance of accounting information in an emerging market. The study was conducted to cover the period from 2014 to 2019 and ninety-eight (98) non-financial quoted entities in Saudi Arabia were used for the study. The dependent variable of the

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study was market value per share while the independent variables were book value per share (BVPS), earnings per share (EPS) and operating cash flow per share (OCFPS). The control variables selected by the researchers were dividend pay-out ratio (DPR), leverage (LV) and industry type (IT). A dummy variable of IFRSs adoption was used in the study. Panel data were collected from the financial statements of the sampled entities. Data were analysed by descriptive statistics and panel regression approach. From the analysis, it was observed that the variables that represented value relevance of accounting information all exerted positive and significant influence on the market value per share of the non-financial entities quoted in Saudi Arabia.

Purwaningrum and Adhikara (2022) conducted a study on does the value relevance of accounting information mediate sustainability reporting disclosures: Empirical evidence of Indonesian capital market. The researchers sought to assess the influence of value relevance of accounting information on stock price. The period of the study ranged from 2015 to 2019. Value relevance of accounting information was measured by return on assets (ROA) being a profitability ratio. Relevant data for the study were collected from the financial statements of the entities sampled for the study. Data were analysed by descriptive statistics and linear regression approach. From the analysis, it was observed that ROA exerted

positive and immaterial influence on stock price of the companies.

Sukmadilaga *et al.* (2023) conducted a study on can accounting value relevance and pricing error influence stock price of high-technology service enterprises? The intention of the researchers was to investigate the influence of accounting value relevance on stock price of high-technology service enterprises. Three hundred and twenty-six (326) technological service enterprises were adopted as the sample size of the study and the key variables that represented accounting value relevance were diluted earnings per share (DEPS), revenue per share (RPS) and book value per share (BVPS). Secondary data were collected from the financial statements of the sampled entities. The data were analysed by descriptive statistics and ordinary least square (OLS) approach. From the analysis, the results showed that DEPS and BVPS exerted positive and significant influence on stock price of the companies while RPS exerted positive and insignificant influence on stock price of the companies studied.

2.3.1 Gap in Empirical Study

Accounting information and market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria is an interesting area of research based on the variables used in this study. Studies have been conducted both locally and internationally in this area of interest but it seems the empirical results derived from previous studies were mixed because of the area of the study, the sectors

studied, the time frame for the study and the measurement of the variables. In the area of the study, several studies in this area were conducted in foreign countries other than Nigeria. These include the study of Vijitha and Nimalathasan (2014) who examined the value relevance of accounting information and share price: A study of listed manufacturing companies in Sri Lanka; Kwon (2018) who conducted a study on the value relevance of accounting information: Focusing on US and China; Tarik (2021) who conducted a study on the value relevance of accounting information and its impact on stock prices: A study on listed pharmaceutical companies at Dhaka stock exchange of Bangladesh; Chehade and Prochazka (2022) who investigated value relevance of accounting information in an emerging market: The case of IFRS adoption by non-financial listed firms in Saudi Arabia and Purwaningrum and Adhikara (2022) who conducted a study on does the value relevance of accounting information mediate sustainability reporting disclosures: Empirical evidence of Indonesian capital market.

Studies in this area of interest conducted internationally with the use of essential variables of accounting information were mostly in quoted manufacturing companies. The study of Okafor *et al.* (2017) in Nigeria was in consumer goods companies only without the inclusion of other sectors such as quoted industrial goods entities. The time frame mostly used in the previous studies were the combination of pre-adoption

and post-adoption periods of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs). In this study, the panel linear regression technique was employed with the inclusion of a control variable of assets turnover ratio (ATR) to achieve unique and different empirical results from previous studies in the extant literature. The measures of market value in previous studies were mostly the adoption of Tobin's Q technique and price-to-book ratio. In the present study, quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria, which made up of quoted consumer goods and industrial goods entities, were used. The post adoption period of IFRSs was strictly considered from 2013 to 2024. The market value in this study was represented by share price. Hence, the need for the present study.

3. Methodology

The *ex-post facto* research design technique was employed in this study because the study required secondary data obtained from the published financial statements of sampled quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. In accordance with the view Kothari and Garg (2014), an empirical study that requires secondary data is one whose relevant data have been published or presented in essential and recognized bulletins and which a researcher could retrieved at any time. This study is a good example whose data were obtained from audited financial statements of the entities sampled for this study. Thus, the adoption of this research design enabled the researcher to examine the

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influence of variables of accounting information on market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

The population of the study was made up of the aggregate quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria whose stocks were traded on the stock market of Nigeria regarded as Nigerian Exchange (NGX) Group Plc. The quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria used in this study were the aggregate of the companies listed under consumer and industrial goods sectors on the floor of NGX Group Plc. The quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria based on the financial year were thirty-one (31) considered by the researcher in this study as the population. The thirty-one (31) quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria were made up of twenty-one (21) companies from consumer goods sector and ten (10) companies from industrial goods sector.

The sample size of this study was drawn from the aggregate population of thirty-one (31) quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria on the floor of NGX Group Plc. Twenty-three (23) quoted manufacturing companies were drawn and sampled for the study from the sub-sectors of consumer goods and industrial goods entities in Nigeria considered. The sample size of twenty-three (23) quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria was made up of fifteen (15) companies drawn from consumer goods sector and eight (8) companies drawn from industrial goods sector. The quoted manufacturing companies used as

the sample size were those with available data for the essential variables of this study and for the period chosen as well as the researcher being able to retrieve the annual reports and audited financial statements.

The purposive sampling technique was employed in this study. This was to enable the researcher to draw an appropriate sample size for this study by considering a suitable technique of selection (Kothari and Garg, 2014). In drawing the sample size, only those companies operating as single entities as well as the possibility of the researcher being able to retrieve the financial statements for the extraction of applicable data in line with the respective variables of this study. The data for the study were collected from the audited financial statements of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria sampled for this study. The secondary data collected from the annual reports and financial statements of quoted manufacturing companies were the ones associated with the key variables of accounting information and market value which included total assets, current liabilities, cash flows from the three components, profit for the year, total liabilities, total equity, total revenue, equity share outstanding and market price per share. The type of secondary data used were panel data obtained from the year 2013 to 2024. The nature of the data and with the objectives of the study necessitated the adoption of panel linear regression approach to establish the influence.

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The relevant data for the study collected from the available financial statements of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria already prepared and published by management of the entities on individual company’s website and on the floor of Nigerian Exchange (NGX) Group Plc (Kothari and Garg, 2014). The published annual reports of the sampled quoted manufacturing entities were retrieved online for data extraction. The dependent variable of this study was market

value measured by share price (SP) while independent variable was accounting information decomposed into Net Assets Per Share (NAPS). From the variable description, the justification for the adoption of panel linear regression approach in establishing the influence of independent variables on dependent variable was clearly observed. These were presented on Table 3.1:

Table 3.1: Variable Description

S/N	Variable	Abbr.	Measurement	Apriori Expectation
1.	Share Price	SP	Share price is measured as the closing stock price per share of a quoted company.	
2.	Net Assets Per Share	NAPS	Net assets per share is measured as total assets less current liabilities divided by equity shares outstanding of a quoted company.	+
3.	Assets Turnover Ratio (Control Variable)	ATR	Assets turnover ratio is measured as total revenue divided by total assets of a quoted company.	+

Source: Researcher’s Compilation (2025)

The key variables of this study as stated on the Table 3.3 regarded as variable description were broadly classified into two and these were accounting information (AI) and market value (MV). Market Value (MV) was measured by Share Price (SP) while accounting information (AIF) was decomposed into sub-variables such as Net Assets Per Share (NAPS). Assets Turnover

Ratio (ATR) was chosen as a control variable in each model. The functional representations of the models were as follows:

$$SP=f(NAPS, ATR) \tag{3.1}$$

The nature of data collected and the objectives of this study suggested the application of panel linear regression technique as a suitable statistical tool to employ in establishing the

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influence of accounting information on market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The panel linear regression approach was considered suitable by the researcher in this study. Based on the gap in the literature and in line with previous studies conducted in the related area of interest, the adapted empirical models were stated appropriately in line with the variables in each of the objectives of this study:

$$SP_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NAPS_{ij} + e_t \quad \text{Equation (3.2)}$$

The formulated models with the inclusion of a control variable were stated accordingly:

$$SP_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NAPS_{ij} + \beta_2 ATR_{ij} + e_t \quad \text{Equation (3.3)}$$

Where: i=Number of companies; j=Number of years and e_t = Error terms.

The models in equation 3.3 was formulated to test the individual influence of accounting information on market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria studied.

The data for this study were analysed using both descriptive and inferential analytical tools. The descriptive statistics was used to examine the nature of the data relating to both accounting information and market value while the

4 Data Analysis and Discussion

4.1 Data Analysis

4.1.1 Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics for the variables was computed and the outcomes were presented on Table

4.1:

inferential statistics was used to establish the influence of variables accounting information on market value measured by share price. In this regard, mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum were the tools used to describe the nature of the applicable data collected. The inferential statistics was panel linear regression approach in accordance with the models formulated. Analyses were performed with the assistance of a statistical software known as E-View-10.

The various statistical tools of the regression used were R^2 , Adjusted R^2 , t-Statistic (t-Stat), variance inflation factor (VIF), Durbin-Watson (DW) Statistic, P-value and F-ratio. P-value is a margin used to either accept or reject hypothesis, VIF was used in the study in testing for the existence of multi-collinearity in the multiple linear regression model while the DW statistic was used in testing for the presence of first order autocorrelation. F-statistics was used to examine the significance of each of the models. All tests were conducted based on 5% level of significance.

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics

Statistics	SP	NAPS	ATR
Mean	89.09239	28.13977	89.39320
Median	19.35000	11.61347	82.42314
Maximum	1556.500	576.8852	473.1307
Minimum	0.460000	-88.95561	3.765040
Std. Dev.	254.9776	51.61601	51.64881
Skewness	4.425038	6.037320	2.440283
Kurtosis	22.46756	55.77392	16.17992
Jarque-Bera	5259.064	33705.16	2271.596
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Sum	24589.50	7766.577	24672.52
Sum Sq. Dev.	17878731	732658.5	733589.9
Observations	276	276	276

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

From Table 4.1, Share Price (SP) had mean of ₦89.092. This indicated that SP of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of this study in average was ₦89.092. The median of ₦19.35 showed the middle value of SP for quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of study. The maximum indicated that the highest value of SP of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of this study was ₦1, 556.50. The minimum indicated that the least value of SP for the period of this study was ₦0.460. The standard deviation indicated that the fluctuations from mean value of SP for quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of this study was ₦254.98 and was high. From Table 4.1, Net Assets Per Share (NAPS) had mean of ₦28.1398. This indicated that NAPS of

quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of this study in average was ₦28.1398. The median of ₦11.614 showed the middle value of NAPS for quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of study. The maximum indicated that the highest value of NAPS of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of this study was ₦576.885. The minimum indicated that the least value of NAPS for the period of this study was ₦88.956. The standard deviation indicated that the fluctuations from mean value of NAPS for quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of this study was ₦51.616 and was high. From Table 4.1, Assets Turnover Ratio (ATR) had mean of 89.39%. This indicated that ATR of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of this study in average was 89.39%.

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The median of 82.42% showed the middle value of ATR for quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of study. The maximum indicated that the highest value of ATR of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria for the period of this study was 473.13%. The minimum indicated that the least value of ATR for the period of this study was 3.765%. The standard deviation indicated that the fluctuations from mean value of ATR for quoted manufacturing

companies in Nigeria for the period of this study was 51.649% and was high.

4.1.2 Correlation Matrix

The association between the variables of this study were ascertained using correlation coefficient. The correlation matrix was meant to ascertain the possible indication of multi-collinearity in the model of this study. The computation of correlation coefficient for all the variables was presented on Table 4.2:

Table 4.2: Correlation Matrix

Correlation	ATR	NAPS	SP
ATR	1.000000		
NAPS	-0.049321	1.000000	
SP	0.107728	0.588212	1.000000
Probability	ATR	NAPS	SP
ATR	-----		
NAPS	0.4144	-----	
SP	0.0740	0.0000	-----

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2025)

From Table 4.2, it was discovered that the relationship between all the independent variables with each other were less than sixty percent (80%). This showed that there was no indication of multi-collinearity in pairs of independent variables of this study. The predictors were independently used to establish the influence of accounting information on market value of quoted manufacturing

companies in Nigeria. The relationship between NAPS and SP was 58.82% (p-value<0.05) and the relationship between ATR and SP was 10.77% (p-value>0.05).

4.1.3 Unit Root Test

The unit root test was conducted on all the variables of this study which were SP, NAPS and ATR. The results of the analysis were presented on Table 4.3:

Table 4.3: Stationarity Test

Method	Statistic	Prob.**
ADF - Fisher Chi-square	519.340	0.0000
ADF - Choi Z-stat	-21.9196	0.0000

** Probabilities for Fisher tests are computed using an asymptotic Chi

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-square distribution. All other tests assume asymptotic normality.

Intermediate ADF test results D(UNTITLED,2)

Series	Prob.	Lag	Max Lag	Obs
D(ATR,2)	0.0000	7	15	266
D(NAPS,2)	0.0000	9	15	264
D(SP,2)	0.0000	4	15	269

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2025)

From Table 4.3, it was observed that all the variables in this study had no problem of variability because of the statistics computed which suggested so. Thus, it showed that the influence of variable of accounting information such as Net Assets Per Share (NAPS) with a control variable of Assets Turnover Ratio (ATR) on Market Value (SP) of quoted manufacturing

companies in Nigeria was not subjected to any variability in a shorter period.

4.1.4 Test of Hypothesis

The pooled panel linear regression analysis was conducted in line with Market Value (SP) and Net Assets Per Share (NAPS) as presented on Table 4.4:

Table 4.4: Pooled Panel Linear Regression

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-54.10514	25.77255	-2.099332	0.0367
NAPS	2.939101	0.238584	12.31891	0.0000
ATR	0.676695	0.238433	2.838093	0.0049
R-squared	0.364737			
Adjusted R-squared	0.360083			
F-statistic	78.37147	Durbin-Watson stat		1.898810
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Dependent Variable: SP

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2025)

From Table 4.4, Net Assets Per Share (NAPS) and Assets Turnover Ratio (ATR) exerted positive and significant influence on market value (SP) of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. This indicated that a percentage increase in NAPS and ATR brought about significant increase in SP of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The result

of the analysis in respect to NAPS and ATR were in compliance with the *a priori* expectation stated by the researcher. The constant value of -N54.105 indicated the value of SP as NAPS and ATR were held constant and significant.

R² indicated that 36.47% variation in SP was attributed to the influence of NAPS and ATR of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria and

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Adjusted R^2 indicated that exact 36.01% variation in SP was attributed to the influence of NAPS of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria and was significant. The Durbin-Watson (DW) statistic of 1.8988 indicated that there was no first-order autocorrelation in the model. The null hypothesis, which states that net assets per share does not significantly influence market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria, was rejected and the alternative hypothesis, which states that net assets per share significantly influence market value of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria, was accepted.

4.2 Discussion of Findings

From Table 4.4, it was observed the Net Assets Per Share (NAPS) exerted positive and significant influence on Market Value (SP) of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. This indicated that as NAPS increases, SP is also improved significantly. The result of the analyses for NAPS was in compliance with the *a priori* expectation. Net assets per share is often computed as the difference between total assets and current liabilities divided by equity shares outstanding of a quoted company in a given accounting period. The size of net assets is an important factor that provides confidence to both potential and existing investors of quoted companies because when net assets are large, it could be said that such company will always generate large revenue in different accounting periods. The composition of the net assets is

often expected to have a greater proportion of non-current assets and a lesser proportion of current assets because of the principle of trade-off between current assets and profitability of an entity.

In other words, when current assets are large, it could be substantiated as a situation whereby larger liquid resources are tied down in the components of inventories and account receivable and as such, profitability is affected negatively because the liquid assets that should have been invested to generate more returns for the company is tied down in the components of current assets. When net assets are made up of greater proportion of non-current assets for a quoted entity, the direction between the variable and indicator of market value is expected to be positive because a greater proportion of non-current assets is expected to generate more revenue to the company as well as maximizing earnings. Thus, net assets is an essential variable of accounting information that provides adequate information to the various users including potential investors especially when the composition of the net assets is properly accumulated. Net assets as an essential variable of accounting information are an embodiment of both non-current and current assets. In the computation of net assets, it is usually anticipated that the accumulated current assets should cover up the current liabilities in any accounting period to avoid the problems of

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illiquidity which might reduce the reputation of the entity.

Acquisition of non-current assets is usually expected to be in line with the purpose or in support of the principal activities of the business. This simply means that a quoted entity is expected to acquire only those non-current assets that are capable of supporting generation of revenue and not those that are just maintained in the organization. Also, in the accumulation of current assets, accounting policies should be stringent ones that will minimize account receivable and larger accumulation of inventories but with cash that will always meet up the obligations or commitments of the organization at any point in time.

In the present study, the positive and significant influence of net assets per share (NAPS) on share price, being a variable of market value, of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria is attributed to the fact that the components of the net asset are directly effective to the operation of the companies in terms of generating adequate revenue as well as meeting the short-term obligations when the need arises. This study was in line with the study of Tarik (2021) who conducted a study on the value relevance of accounting information and its impact on stock prices: A study on listed pharmaceutical companies at Dhaka stock exchange of Bangladesh and found that net assets value per share exerted positive and significant influence on share price of firms. The study was also

consistent with Vijitha and Nimalathan (2014) who examined the value relevance of accounting information and share price: A study of listed manufacturing companies in Sri Lanka and found that accounting information exerted direct and substantial influence on stock price of the firms studied.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

The study was conducted to ascertain the influence of accounting information on market value (SP) of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The individual variables of accounting information were Net Assets Per Share (NAPS) was selected by the researcher as control variable to reduce the spuriousness of the empirical results in individual models. From the analysis, it was concluded that accounting information had a significant influence on market value (SP) of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria from 2013 to 2024.

In accordance with the empirical results arrived at, the following recommendations were suggested as follows:

- i. The managers of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria should raise net assets per share by acquiring more of non-current assets to improve upon the market value of the entities.

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APPENDIX ONE (i)**Table A: Computed Data for the Study from 2013 to 2024**

Company	Year	SP (₦)	NAPS (₦)	ATR (%)
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2013	91.94	9.20	82.83
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2014	40.00	4.72	105.89
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2015	17.15	8.93	97.92
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2016	10.29	8.29	105.59
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2017	15.67	8.46	116.38
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2018	10.00	9.29	130.68
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2019	10.55	10.06	136.54
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2020	9.00	9.98	106.61
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2021	8.80	11.53	96.99
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2022	11.50	12.05	92.46
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2023	17.30	3.87	105.13
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2024	23.00	2.28	178.30
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2013	70.25	58.40	100.78
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2014	61.81	57.95	111.61
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2015	33.50	43.98	99.24
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2016	19.40	45.27	106.25
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2017	17.98	48.21	109.10
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2018	37.30	44.52	120.70
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2019	18.00	42.86	117.88
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2020	21.25	52.10	125.65
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2021	28.80	62.25	140.90
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2022	31.05	67.07	170.79
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2023	31.00	67.16	128.32
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2024	30.50	79.59	129.09
Guinness Nig. Plc	2013	251.71	46.34	101.16
Guinness Nig. Plc	2014	189.21	58.49	82.52
Guinness Nig. Plc	2015	162.81	50.57	96.93
Guinness Nig. Plc	2016	103.40	46.41	74.44
Guinness Nig. Plc	2017	67.95	54.66	86.22

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Guinness Nig. Plc	2018	97.75	50.41	93.29
Guinness Nig. Plc	2019	47.65	51.10	81.78
Guinness Nig. Plc	2020	14.50	38.14	72.41
Guinness Nig. Plc	2021	29.00	39.47	94.69
Guinness Nig. Plc	2022	90.50	46.53	95.90
Guinness Nig. Plc	2023	59.95	26.51	94.91
Guinness Nig. Plc	2024	61.90	1.57	132.44

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

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Table A: Computed Data for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	SP (₦)	NAPS (₦)	ATR (%)
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2013	2.94	3.52	82.45
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2014	3.87	4.51	86.30
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2015	3.00	4.55	72.20
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2016	1.46	4.01	66.91
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2017	1.05	10.95	47.04
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2018	2.55	12.18	57.26
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2019	1.20	12.01	54.11
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2020	0.98	11.18	56.55
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2021	1.18	10.78	74.35
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2022	3.50	10.43	91.03
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2023	3.13	9.44	89.30
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2024	3.15	7.59	126.41
Int Breweries Plc	2013	20.95	4.65	75.48
Int Breweries Plc	2014	24.20	5.39	75.89
Int Breweries Plc	2015	18.90	6.13	68.44
Int Breweries Plc	2016	20.49	5.32	69.50
Int Breweries Plc	2017	54.50	7.46	15.73
Int Breweries Plc	2018	30.50	22.27	38.87
Int Breweries Plc	2019	9.50	18.73	36.25
Int Breweries Plc	2020	5.95	5.76	36.71
Int Breweries Plc	2021	4.95	5.37	38.79
Int Breweries Plc	2022	4.70	10.18	45.15
Int Breweries Plc	2023	4.94	19.22	36.05
Int Breweries Plc	2024	5.50	14.50	67.18
N Nig. Flour Plc	2013	23.80	11.16	322.95
N Nig. Flour Plc	2014	22.05	11.67	348.74
N Nig. Flour Plc	2015	17.15	1.03	473.13
N Nig. Flour Plc	2016	6.65	2.26	53.12
N Nig. Flour Plc	2017	6.31	7.62	30.68
N Nig. Flour Plc	2018	6.55	14.27	48.36

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N Nig. Flour Plc	2019	4.30	11.83	83.12
N Nig. Flour Plc	2020	4.30	20.81	104.11
N Nig. Flour Plc	2021	6.20	19.82	117.68
N Nig. Flour Plc	2022	9.00	19.77	114.40
N Nig. Flour Plc	2023	11.95	42.83	90.66
N Nig. Flour Plc	2024	48.30	51.39	128.05

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

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Table A: Computed Data for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	SP (₦)	NAPS (₦)	ATR (%)
Nascon Allied Plc	2013	14.99	2.88	94.80
Nascon Allied Plc	2014	6.22	2.72	89.60
Nascon Allied Plc	2015	7.15	3.15	99.28
Nascon Allied Plc	2016	8.50	3.58	74.35
Nascon Allied Plc	2017	18.50	5.10	89.85
Nascon Allied Plc	2018	18.00	5.35	85.13
Nascon Allied Plc	2019	12.95	7.52	71.09
Nascon Allied Plc	2020	14.50	7.09	63.22
Nascon Allied Plc	2021	13.20	7.66	82.13
Nascon Allied Plc	2022	11.00	9.45	105.86
Nascon Allied Plc	2023	60.39	12.81	96.69
Nascon Allied Plc	2024	38.00	19.30	153.35
Nestle Nig. Plc	2013	1,200.00	95.11	122.99
Nestle Nig. Plc	2014	1,011.75	78.17	135.14
Nestle Nig. Plc	2015	860.00	75.04	126.89
Nestle Nig. Plc	2016	810.00	61.25	107.27
Nestle Nig. Plc	2017	1,555.99	84.68	166.31
Nestle Nig. Plc	2018	1,485.00	88.58	164.03
Nestle Nig. Plc	2019	1,469.90	85.58	146.88
Nestle Nig. Plc	2020	1,505.00	101.12	116.61
Nestle Nig. Plc	2021	1,556.50	144.73	113.40
Nestle Nig. Plc	2022	963.90	248.08	107.66
Nestle Nig. Plc	2023	1,090.00	367.29	94.04
Nestle Nig. Plc	2024	975.00	576.89	111.66
Nig. Breweries Plc	2013	134.32	32.98	76.82
Nig. Breweries Plc	2014	132.24	31.03	76.27
Nig. Breweries Plc	2015	108.80	27.25	82.39
Nig. Breweries Plc	2016	118.39	28.10	85.34
Nig. Breweries Plc	2017	107.92	28.26	95.58
Nig. Breweries Plc	2018	68.40	31.06	90.09

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Nig. Breweries Plc	2019	47.20	30.39	84.44
Nig. Breweries Plc	2020	44.80	29.43	75.83
Nig. Breweries Plc	2021	40.00	26.66	90.58
Nig. Breweries Plc	2022	41.00	72.67	88.60
Nig. Breweries Plc	2023	37.00	26.68	75.19
Nig. Breweries Plc	2024	32.00	16.63	95.44

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

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Table A: Computed Data for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	SP (₦)	NAPS (₦)	ATR (%)
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2013	26.89	23.98	114.19
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2014	26.89	24.67	83.32
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2015	26.52	25.52	51.93
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2016	24.82	26.93	61.57
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2017	24.44	27.03	43.39
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2018	22.10	21.98	36.08
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2019	22.10	18.84	16.89
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2020	22.10	14.31	9.98
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2021	19.90	10.50	6.44
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2022	16.20	4.91	8.05
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2023	17.75	25.36	3.77
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2024	19.30	-8.63	28.74
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2013	50.98	12.82	98.68
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2014	36.00	11.84	102.73
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2015	29.18	7.64	152.01
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2016	20.61	9.55	123.58
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2017	18.36	9.58	74.98
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2018	20.85	9.42	78.42
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2019	8.10	9.58	73.39
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2020	5.50	7.77	65.46
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2021	5.50	7.44	68.95
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2022	11.45	7.37	72.94
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2023	16.90	7.22	60.84
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2024	22.00	11.01	76.88
Unilever Nig. Plc	2013	53.80	4.14	137.14
Unilever Nig. Plc	2014	35.80	3.67	121.90
Unilever Nig. Plc	2015	41.15	4.09	118.04
Unilever Nig. Plc	2016	35.05	5.02	96.26
Unilever Nig. Plc	2017	41.00	14.69	70.36
Unilever Nig. Plc	2018	37.00	15.44	70.46

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Unilever Nig. Plc	2019	22.00	11.99	58.34
Unilever Nig. Plc	2020	13.90	11.09	67.70
Unilever Nig. Plc	2021	14.50	11.85	65.13
Unilever Nig. Plc	2022	11.60	12.19	70.64
Unilever Nig. Plc	2023	18.65	14.36	89.32
Unilever Nig. Plc	2024	38.00	15.80	105.56

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

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Table A: Computed Data for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	SP (₦)	NAPS (₦)	ATR (%)
Berger Paints Plc	2013	8.00	9.76	74.73
Berger Paints Plc	2014	8.55	9.74	84.69
Berger Paints Plc	2015	10.00	9.50	77.58
Berger Paints Plc	2016	6.40	9.65	63.45
Berger Paints Plc	2017	8.48	11.15	69.88
Berger Paints Plc	2018	8.60	11.21	74.47
Berger Paints Plc	2019	6.75	12.35	70.76
Berger Paints Plc	2020	7.35	12.57	77.19
Berger Paints Plc	2021	8.55	12.67	97.15
Berger Paints Plc	2022	6.00	13.24	114.53
Berger Paints Plc	2023	17.35	15.71	119.65
Berger Paints Plc	2024	21.00	16.22	142.53
Beta Glass Plc	2013	12.02	35.49	51.89
Beta Glass Plc	2014	23.15	38.51	61.77
Beta Glass Plc	2015	44.54	43.29	58.71
Beta Glass Plc	2016	25.27	52.39	57.53
Beta Glass Plc	2017	42.76	58.34	58.06
Beta Glass Plc	2018	56.92	64.72	57.12
Beta Glass Plc	2019	44.83	74.10	56.47
Beta Glass Plc	2020	46.17	78.31	47.51
Beta Glass Plc	2021	44.12	91.43	58.60
Beta Glass Plc	2022	39.60	83.01	71.55
Beta Glass Plc	2023	59.40	172.20	58.87
Beta Glass Plc	2024	71.50	120.69	85.60
Champion B. Plc	2013	16.91	-5.05	24.44
Champion B. Plc	2014	6.98	0.84	34.43
Champion B. Plc	2015	3.38	0.93	33.90
Champion B. Plc	2016	2.45	0.99	38.80
Champion B. Plc	2017	2.08	1.08	47.35
Champion B. Plc	2018	1.99	1.04	45.43

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Champion B. Plc	2019	0.95	1.08	63.08
Champion B. Plc	2020	0.86	1.16	62.03
Champion B. Plc	2021	2.35	1.28	77.99
Champion B. Plc	2022	5.50	1.60	79.52
Champion B. Plc	2023	3.09	1.60	61.87
Champion B. Plc	2024	3.95	1.36	97.87

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

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Table A: Computed Data for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	SP (₦)	NAPS (₦)	ATR (%)
BUA Cement Plc	2013	11.75	8.72	101.68
BUA Cement Plc	2014	10.35	9.77	95.81
BUA Cement Plc	2015	9.35	10.35	76.04
BUA Cement Plc	2016	4.76	11.56	70.33
BUA Cement Plc	2017	9.50	13.91	79.47
BUA Cement Plc	2018	19.40	25.58	9.12
BUA Cement Plc	2019	18.10	26.12	9.01
BUA Cement Plc	2020	77.35	16.48	27.33
BUA Cement Plc	2021	67.05	17.22	35.32
BUA Cement Plc	2022	97.75	25.05	41.30
BUA Cement Plc	2023	185.00	24.76	37.84
BUA Cement Plc	2024	93.00	29.41	55.81
Cutix Plc	2013	1.46	0.77	179.68
Cutix Plc	2014	1.90	1.19	128.10
Cutix Plc	2015	1.82	1.19	119.79
Cutix Plc	2016	1.39	1.29	149.91
Cutix Plc	2017	0.89	1.38	157.77
Cutix Plc	2018	2.95	1.68	178.31
Cutix Plc	2019	1.85	0.52	189.91
Cutix Plc	2020	0.61	0.66	138.52
Cutix Plc	2021	1.11	0.71	140.49
Cutix Plc	2022	2.44	0.85	154.38
Cutix Plc	2023	2.25	0.98	159.14
Cutix Plc	2024	3.10	1.29	168.69
Dang. Cem. Plc	2013	218.99	39.36	45.22
Dang. Cem. Plc	2014	200.00	44.46	38.56
Dang. Cem. Plc	2015	170.00	57.74	34.61
Dang. Cem. Plc	2016	173.78	65.28	28.36
Dang. Cem. Plc	2017	230.00	74.36	34.29
Dang. Cem. Plc	2018	189.70	84.34	35.91

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Dang. Cem. Plc	2019	142.00	82.95	33.46
Dang. Cem. Plc	2020	244.90	92.57	34.02
Dang. Cem. Plc	2021	257.00	102.37	38.47
Dang. Cem. Plc	2022	261.00	110.48	45.34
Dang. Cem. Plc	2023	763.00	114.04	42.26
Dang. Cem. Plc	2024	394.00	204.35	42.21

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

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Table A: Computed Data for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	SP (₦)	NAPS (₦)	ATR (%)
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2013	11.70	5.07	117.63
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2014	6.35	5.34	96.73
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2015	6.03	5.23	102.88
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2016	5.90	5.93	156.94
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2017	20.00	8.87	100.03
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2018	15.25	9.37	82.09
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2019	13.60	9.35	45.01
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2020	17.60	11.24	79.59
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2021	17.40	11.70	79.01
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2022	16.05	15.30	82.13
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2023	67.90	6.76	73.45
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2024	36.00	18.08	65.37
Lafarge Africa Plc	2013	115.00	40.16	60.78
Lafarge Africa Plc	2014	73.18	69.73	30.80
Lafarge Africa Plc	2015	88.00	73.27	30.05
Lafarge Africa Plc	2016	38.91	77.55	16.22
Lafarge Africa Plc	2017	43.60	59.85	28.75
Lafarge Africa Plc	2018	12.45	46.56	32.38
Lafarge Africa Plc	2019	15.30	25.51	37.68
Lafarge Africa Plc	2020	21.05	23.64	40.08
Lafarge Africa Plc	2021	23.95	24.84	49.11
Lafarge Africa Plc	2022	24.00	27.27	55.92
Lafarge Africa Plc	2023	36.00	-88.96	54.00
Lafarge Africa Plc	2024	71.00	36.41	65.26
Meyer Paints Plc	2013	1.41	5.68	57.75
Meyer Paints Plc	2014	0.91	5.37	55.03
Meyer Paints Plc	2015	0.67	5.85	51.59
Meyer Paints Plc	2016	0.90	4.78	50.08
Meyer Paints Plc	2017	0.73	1.24	58.02
Meyer Paints Plc	2018	0.59	1.58	52.75

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Meyer Paints Plc	2019	0.54	1.52	29.73
Meyer Paints Plc	2020	0.50	3.37	28.03
Meyer Paints Plc	2021	0.46	2.07	56.28
Meyer Paints Plc	2022	2.27	2.89	75.22
Meyer Paints Plc	2023	3.56	3.35	93.48
Meyer Paints Plc	2024	9.25	3.67	111.05

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

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Table A: Computed Data for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	SP (₦)	NAPS (₦)	ATR (%)
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2013	2.78	10.17	165.52
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2014	2.98	10.67	140.68
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2015	4.92	5.07	129.15
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2016	2.39	5.11	93.06
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2017	2.09	5.14	122.71
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2018	2.92	6.98	116.20
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2019	3.90	6.31	164.50
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2020	6.00	9.71	108.68
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2021	17.10	11.56	107.79
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2022	20.95	13.35	114.13
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2023	22.45	14.07	102.25
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2024	22.00	21.75	160.09
CAP Plc	2013	48.45	1.93	204.14
CAP Plc	2014	38.00	1.79	226.81
CAP Plc	2015	37.60	2.25	206.99
CAP Plc	2016	30.55	3.46	138.61
CAP Plc	2017	34.60	3.35	141.88
CAP Plc	2018	34.85	4.19	121.53
CAP Plc	2019	24.00	3.85	124.40
CAP Plc	2020	20.00	5.35	104.11
CAP Plc	2021	19.45	5.81	117.27
CAP Plc	2022	17.80	8.51	143.28
CAP Plc	2023	24.00	10.39	155.40
CAP Plc	2024	47.00	14.44	184.79

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

Jeremiah Patrick EDET, PhD, ACA, Raphael Sunday ETIM, PhD, FCA, FCNA, FCTI and Akpanuko ESSIEN, PhD

APPENDIX TWO (ii)

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2024

Company	Year	REV (₦'000)	TA (₦'000)	PAT (₦'000)	CL (₦'000)	TE (₦'000)	NCFO (₦'000)	NCFI (₦'000)	NCCF (₦'000)	ESO (Unit)
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2013	35,760,753.0	43,172,624.0	6,023,220.0	14,386,781.0	23,994,931.0	6,621,476.0	2,977,964.0	3,136,485.0	3,130,374.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2014	30,518,586.0	28,820,107.0	1,512,687.0	14,042,218.0	11,542,026.0	1,419,524.0	1,129,439.0	14,354,137.0	3,130,374.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2015	27,825,194.0	28,417,005.0	1,153,295.0	11,651,634.0	12,285,297.0	5,797,705.0	787,360.0	1,270,811.0	1,878,202.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2016	29,979,410.0	28,392,951.0	296,402.0	12,820,278.0	11,056,734.0	-61,766.0	221,081.0	478,323.0	1,878,202.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2017	33,079,446.0	28,423,121.0	299,998.0	12,529,586.0	11,742,791.0	1,471,632.0	950,998.0	258,655.0	1,878,202.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2018	35,973,479.0	27,528,040.0	823,085.0	10,085,404.0	12,676,146.0	6,695,082.0	722,841.0	2,578,012.0	1,878,202.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2019	39,326,807.0	28,801,938.0	1,070,845.0	9,901,393.0	13,566,235.0	2,285,899.0	1,515,541.0	431,344.0	1,878,202.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2020	35,407,323.0	33,210,684.0	931,827.0	14,474,694.0	13,549,523.0	4,254,793.0	845,019.0	3,246,691.0	1,878,202.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2021	42,372,034.0	43,688,291.0	449,712.0	22,024,707.0	13,636,354.0	674,014.0	726,317.0	6,697,497.0	1,878,202.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2022	55,212,617.0	59,713,684.0	583,111.0	37,088,401.0	13,302,628.0	2,534,928.0	694,897.0	12,692,504.0	1,878,202.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2023	80,378,955.0	76,458,376.0	19,089,704.0	69,193,515.0	6,513,678.0	2,797,230.0	1,433,138.0	9,473,254.0	1,878,202.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2024	129,165,095.0	72,443,944.0	22,224,942.0	67,241,651.0	4,379,193.0	20,109,534.0	4,498,234.0	13,624,812.0	2,280,284.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2013	225,629,747.0	223,889,726.0	8,900,989.0	84,562,515.0	87,463,784.0	527,216.0	9,693,976.0	19,025,249.0	2,385,684.0

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Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2014	245,701,366.0	220,145,554.0	10,465,518.0	81,893,576.0	89,678,463.0	9,934,541.0	-	3,308,781.0	34,249,281.0	2,385,684.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2015	229,777,869.0	231,529,878.0	2,419,544.0	116,115,447.0	96,651,666.0	10,096,781.0	-	5,720,460.0	14,990,590.0	2,624,252.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2016	247,876,504.0	233,296,607.0	10,425,786.0	114,508,685.0	100,244,139.0	20,924,187.0	-	23,900,756.0	1,906,428.0	2,624,252.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2017	375,225,284.0	343,933,157.0	9,829,046.0	217,412,600.0	108,115,699.0	14,328,877.0	-	27,311,825.0	21,107,005.0	2,624,252.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2018	389,397,836.0	322,604,582.0	9,244,729.0	140,074,526.0	151,446,296.0	24,037,585.0	-	54,158,200.0	22,394,367.0	4,100,394.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2019	370,205,529.0	314,058,187.0	19,317,654.0	138,329,706.0	138,929,273.0	3,544,753.0	-	34,258,841.0	29,077,558.0	4,100,394.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2020	394,884,217.0	314,267,060.0	12,582,571.0	100,624,270.0	146,316,890.0	72,239,224.0	-	24,989,243.0	42,011,798.0	4,100,394.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2021	535,881,585.0	380,322,525.0	20,172,489.0	125,066,314.0	159,878,794.0	10,478,062.0	-	9,176,062.0	11,575,002.0	4,100,394.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2022	832,810,561.0	487,617,576.0	21,819,816.0	212,620,619.0	174,663,847.0	51,219.0	-	1,448,389.0	13,795,610.0	4,100,394.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2023	923,015,713.0	719,285,322.0	14,173,904.0	443,900,217.0	181,820,527.0	14,728,972.0	-	14,137,836.0	60,038,437.0	4,100,394.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2024	1,346,992,354.0	1,043,445,303.0	16,817,754.0	717,075,540.0	192,333,092.0	23,148,591.0	-	23,327,794.0	47,340,470.0	4,100,394.0

Source: Financial Statements of Selected Quoted Companies in Nigeria for Various Years

Jeremiah Patrick EDET, PhD, ACA, Raphael Sunday ETIM, PhD, FCA, FCNA, FCTI and Akpanuko ESSIEN, PhD

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	REV (₦'000)	TA (₦'000)	PAT (₦'000)	CL (₦'000)	TE (₦'000)	NCFO (₦'000)	NCFI (₦'000)	NCFF (₦'000)	ESO (Unit)
Guinness Nig. Plc	2013	122,463,538.0	121,060,621.0	5,145,149.0	51,275,097.0	121,060,621.0	24,298,136.0	14,081,901.0	10,617,820.0	1,505,888.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2014	109,202,120.0	132,328,273.0	2,108,800.0	44,248,749.0	132,328,273.0	19,157,202.0	13,683,695.0	3,304,804.0	1,505,888.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2015	118,495,882.0	122,246,632.0	7,794,899.0	46,100,344.0	48,341,376.0	32,538,985.0	8,454,576.0	21,361,905.0	1,505,888.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2016	101,973,030.0	136,992,444.0	2,015,886.0	67,109,622.0	41,660,605.0	1,320,097.0	8,532,239.0	8,425,931.0	1,505,888.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2017	125,919,817.0	146,038,216.0	1,923,720.0	63,719,662.0	42,943,015.0	18,045,541.0	7,568,324.0	11,294,243.0	1,505,888.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2018	142,975,792.0	153,254,968.0	6,717,605.0	42,847,115.0	87,588,174.0	10,589,789.0	15,629,170.0	13,366,905.0	2,190,382.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2019	131,498,373.0	160,792,627.0	5,483,732.0	48,856,474.0	89,060,462.0	13,406,042.0	15,827,676.0	6,730,383.0	2,190,382.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2020	104,376,015.0	144,145,581.0	12,578,818.0	60,597,976.0	73,038,140.0	15,296,613.0	10,415,135.0	1,719,206.0	2,190,382.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2021	160,416,257.0	169,406,525.0	1,255,338.0	82,958,885.0	74,286,575.0	52,380,639.0	11,376,970.0	10,268,532.0	2,190,382.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2022	206,822,127.0	215,660,208.0	15,651,362.0	113,732,630.0	89,979,391.0	28,118,793.0	6,844,120.0	12,051,632.0	2,190,382.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2023	229,440,861.0	241,748,144.0	18,168,041.0	183,671,423.0	56,424,616.0	34,379,964.0	6,317,423.0	8,884,690.0	2,190,382.0

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Guinness Nig. Plc	2024	299,489,774.0	226,130,077.0	54,766,776.0	222,684,738.0	2,161,466.0	80,139,988.0	6,222,140.0	123,799,125.0	2,190,382.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2013	45,709,382.0	55,437,478.0	2,843,520.0	27,503,156.0	18,553,083.0	1,794,859.0	6,603,263.0	7,774,043.0	7,930,198.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2014	55,084,305.0	63,830,439.0	3,351,564.0	28,059,339.0	20,605,248.0	6,431,524.0	2,261,332.0	3,166,233.0	7,930,198.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2015	49,057,511.0	67,943,444.0	1,120,267.0	31,860,220.0	20,315,834.0	5,602,147.0	14,749,582.0	2,466,019.0	7,930,198.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2016	50,883,780.0	76,046,576.0	3,023,852.0	44,213,225.0	16,362,599.0	10,131,641.0	6,046,484.0	7,521,745.0	7,930,198.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2017	53,227,891.0	113,151,715.0	4,304,955.0	26,318,698.0	52,334,665.0	2,533,081.0	15,856,863.0	9,746,464.0	7,930,198.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2018	71,476,319.0	124,835,013.0	4,426,978.0	28,207,258.0	56,391,664.0	14,725,910.0	5,975,524.0	8,506,031.0	7,930,198.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2019	74,409,113.0	137,505,112.0	68,368.0	42,301,619.0	56,667,969.0	9,413,187.0	5,649,275.0	194,141.0	7,930,198.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2020	80,450,397.0	142,261,292.0	650,492.0	53,639,919.0	57,285,793.0	5,417,298.0	2,595,247.0	1,317,342.0	7,930,198.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2021	109,594,730.0	147,394,656.0	1,125,864.0	61,940,563.0	57,968,678.0	12,880,439.0	741,759.0	1,238,706.0	7,930,198.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2022	136,427,507.0	149,869,159.0	983,812.0	67,182,805.0	56,429,751.0	553,009.0	1,300,350.0	4,698,685.0	7,930,198.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2023	147,350,739.0	164,999,977.0	256,113.0	90,173,174.0	32,976,289.0	4,115,393.0	6,915,289.0	5,368,495.0	7,930,198.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2024	188,311,035.0	148,965,948.0	10,119,778.0	88,779,107.0	22,856,511.0	70,737,069.0	1,801,355.0	71,910,777.0	7,930,198.0

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Source: Financial Statements of Selected Quoted Companies in Nigeria for Various Years

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	REV (₦'000)	TA (₦'000)	PAT (₦'000)	CL (₦'000)	TE (₦'000)	NCFO (₦'000)	NCFI (₦'000)	NCFE (₦'000)	ESO (Unit)
Int Breweries Plc	2013	17,388,632.0	23,036,762.0	2,327,342.0	7,859,335.0	9,380,173.0	4,043,424.0	6,718,935.0	11,486,402.0	3,262,526.0
Int Breweries Plc	2014	18,493,907.0	24,370,540.0	2,105,500.0	6,604,447.0	11,269,923.0	6,258,083.0	4,097,426.0	2,809,671.0	3,294,250.0
Int Breweries Plc	2015	20,649,295.0	30,171,590.0	2,395,178.0	9,975,208.0	12,168,259.0	3,151,232.0	5,754,930.0	3,063,987.0	3,294,250.0
Int Breweries Plc	2016	23,269,364.0	33,482,106.0	2,979,874.0	15,940,734.0	13,997,391.0	7,901,718.0	3,946,605.0	3,706,723.0	3,294,250.0
Int Breweries Plc	2017	36,527,807.0	232,149,251.0	1,395,225.0	168,026,156.0	39,225,363.0	44,789,617.0	42,580,971.0	11,016,915.0	8,595,862.0
Int Breweries Plc	2018	120,610,825.0	310,278,920.0	3,866,298.0	118,879,435.0	35,160,923.0	30,936,156.0	70,202,176.0	101,778,163.0	8,595,862.0
Int Breweries Plc	2019	132,351,500.0	365,146,533.0	27,790,666.0	204,106,062.0	7,463,701.0	41,686,120.0	58,647,254.0	59,795,928.0	8,595,862.0
Int Breweries Plc	2020	136,790,573.0	372,646,406.0	12,365,082.0	217,921,521.0	151,733,857.0	52,227,989.0	29,959,433.0	3,267,073.0	26,862,068.0
Int Breweries Plc	2021	182,298,045.0	469,953,215.0	17,656,510.0	325,679,434.0	135,303,901.0	52,041,595.0	86,496,101.0	50,448,845.0	26,862,068.0
Int Breweries Plc	2022	218,650,266.0	484,251,740.0	21,626,290.0	210,841,321.0	117,330,433.0	42,666,952.0	66,524,156.0	6,919,758.0	26,862,068.0
Int Breweries Plc	2023	264,278,299.0	733,113,172.0	59,467,375.0	216,721,161.0	124,577,455.0	74,845,867.0	50,088,565.0	31,379,888.0	26,862,068.0
Int Breweries Plc	2024	488,955,682.0	727,872,297.0	113,614,900.0	256,228,762.0	448,914,077.0	148,925,789.0	89,714,760.0	81,053,542.0	32,519,250.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2013	11,701,741.0	3,623,417.0	225,145.0	1,634,103.0	1,605,717.0	1,125,731.0	246,182.0	-27,030.0	178,200.0

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N Nig. Flour Plc	2014	11,392,017.0	3,266,615.0	233,545.0	1,187,714.0	1,773,912.0	-55,295.0	41,487.0	-85,327.0	178,200.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2015	10,529,075.0	2,225,405.0	-199,558.0	293,638.0	1,480,063.0	555,099.0	-68,046.0	-71,280.0	1,884,306.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2016	979,038.0	1,843,217.0	-197,240.0	90,908.0	1,250,937.0	-527,392.0	27,218.0	-53,460.0	777,038.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2017	1,330,536.0	4,337,444.0	-18,042.0	2,980,114.0	1,239,578.0	-871,530.0	1,438,714.0	2,391,664.0	178,200.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2018	2,861,752.0	5,917,639.0	-60,988.0	3,374,312.0	1,174,262.0	-268,417.0	268,819.0	623,605.0	178,200.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2019	4,149,917.0	4,992,912.0	-31,696.0	2,885,324.0	1,150,712.0	1,220,540.0	-105,361.0	-1,248,704.0	178,200.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2020	8,841,135.0	8,491,986.0	64,635.0	4,783,206.0	2,768,993.0	31,939,819.0	12,175,448.0	38,154,460.0	178,200.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2021	8,667,751.0	7,365,270.0	69,919.0	3,833,773.0	2,787,771.0	-298,921.0	-31,233.0	-1,459,739.0	178,200.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2022	15,232,820.0	13,315,128.0	80,668.0	9,791,386.0	2,854,469.0	2,271,879.0	-514,610.0	-1,316,333.0	178,200.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2023	16,161,840.0	17,827,833.0	272,820.0	10,195,986.0	6,579,567.0	1,226,660.0	-179,945.0	-247,076.0	178,200.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2024	22,951,365.0	17,924,446.0	1,525,895.0	8,766,651.0	8,077,739.0	1,663,173.0	197,686.0	238,765.0	178,200.0

Source: Financial Statements of Selected Quoted Companies in Nigeria for Various Years

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Comp any	Ye ar	REV (₦'000)	TA (₦'000)	PAT (₦'000)	CL (₦'000)	TE (₦'000)	NCFO (₦'000)	NCFI (₦'000)	NCFF (₦'000)	ESO (Unit)
Nascon Allied Plc	2013	10,837,261.0	11,431,167.0	2,699,542.0	3,806,716.0	6,892,626.0	1,881,899.0	2,362,290.0	2,392,812.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2014	11,250,544.0	12,555,885.0	1,867,038.0	5,346,115.0	6,307,306.0	4,194,319.0	2,114,952.0	2,384,495.0	2,649,438.0

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Nascon Allied Plc	2015	16,178,197.0	16,294,826.0	2,105,646.0	7,951,500.0	1,324,719.0	4,007,770.0	1,002,044.0	1,344,784.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2016	18,291,792.0	24,603,267.0	2,415,183.0	15,124,953.0	2,415,183.0	2,238,497.0	475,023.0	1,814,862.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2017	27,064,325.0	30,123,247.0	2,565,896.0	16,615,330.0	1,854,607.0	13,835,753.0	4,924,362.0	1,926,720.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2018	25,769,352.0	30,270,429.0	2,029,168.0	16,088,720.0	3,974,158.0	1,021,757.0	3,936,363.0	3,974,158.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2019	27,487,788.0	38,668,792.0	1,845,243.0	18,742,264.0	11,089,285.0	6,090,389.0	5,445,382.0	427,751.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2020	28,010,059.0	44,308,991.0	2,690,310.0	25,521,662.0	12,719,820.0	8,020,924.0	3,984,916.0	5,094,372.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2021	33,279,688.0	40,521,398.0	2,970,982.0	20,218,075.0	14,630,680.0	4,995,649.0	1,098,432.0	1,675,884.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2022	58,786,251.0	55,530,771.0	5,496,248.0	30,489,559.0	19,042,366.0	3,499,588.0	895,974.0	3,360,120.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2023	80,828,373.0	83,591,991.0	13,728,369.0	49,659,750.0	27,471,858.0	20,049,817.0	893,510.0	6,321,250.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2024	120,387,151.0	78,502,487.0	15,583,602.0	26,337,166.0	43,055,460.0	4,164,628.0	562,308.0	4,217,064.0	2,702,426.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2013	133,084,076.0	108,207,480.0	22,258,279.0	32,817,482.0	23,004,468.0	35,216,402.0	7,030,198.0	18,283,766.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2014	143,328,982.0	106,062,067.0	22,235,640.0	44,103,244.0	30,056,784.0	23,495,038.0	7,263,538.0	27,481,104.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2015	151,271,526.0	119,215,053.0	23,736,777.0	59,731,857.0	38,007,074.0	39,877,436.0	7,228,711.0	22,491,122.0	792,656.0

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Nestle Nig. Plc	2016	181,910,977.0	169,585,932.0	7,924,968.0	121,033,434.0	30,878,075.0	61,484,847.0	-2,842,594.0	-20,070,185.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2017	244,151,411.0	146,804,128.0	33,723,730.0	79,680,495.0	44,878,177.0	19,235,881.0	-2,433,312.0	-56,574,372.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2018	266,274,621.0	162,334,442.0	43,008,026.0	92,117,501.0	50,220,486.0	74,618,791.0	-10,984,275.0	-60,690,925.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2019	284,035,255.0	193,374,314.0	45,683,113.0	125,535,430.0	45,557,630.0	49,945,530.0	-12,328,813.0	-47,743,062.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2020	287,084,087.0	246,184,996.0	39,212,025.0	166,030,351.0	29,296,984.0	97,196,104.0	-15,718,617.0	-27,018,843.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2021	351,822,329.0	310,238,504.0	40,037,277.0	195,517,985.0	21,378,209.0	65,927,085.0	-19,969,328.0	-4,449,023.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2022	446,819,260.0	415,044,031.0	48,965,488.0	218,404,562.0	30,291,224.0	4,432,963.0	-22,868,150.0	-44,241,769.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2023	547,118,754.0	581,774,407.0	79,473,781.0	290,637,709.0	78,035,156.0	82,702,831.0	-55,112,317.0	-21,293,339.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2024	958,814,739.0	858,698,352.0	164,592,022.0	401,426,871.0	92,289,917.0	5,858,732.0	-69,160,262.0	-84,244,062.0	792,656.0

Source: Financial Statements of Selected Quoted Companies in Nigeria for Various Years

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	REV (N'ooo)	TA (N'ooo)	PAT (N'ooo)	CL (N'ooo)	TE (N'ooo)	NCFO (N'ooo)	NCFI (N'ooo)	NCFE (N'ooo)	ESO (Unit)
Nig. Breweries Plc	2013	268,613,518.0	349,676,784.0	43,080,349.0	100,295,715.0	112,359,185.0	95,167,850.0	-32,514,198.0	-62,639,009.0	7,562,706.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2014	266,372,475.0	349,229,163.0	42,520,253.0	114,554,626.0	171,964,263.0	60,860,045.0	-28,591,797.0	-36,328,397.0	7,562,706.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2015	293,905,792.0	356,707,123.0	38,049,518.0	140,655,590.0	172,233,465.0	72,673,843.0	-32,360,293.0	-59,891,524.0	7,929,102.0

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Nig. Breweries Plc	2016	313,743,147.0	367,639,915.0	28,396,777.0	144,856,800.0	165,805,542.0	70,210,871.0	-18,808,968.0	-26,007,985.0	7,929,102.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2017	365,798,057.0	382,726,540.0	33,009,292.0	156,698,905.0	178,150,934.0	72,113,517.0	-32,065,023.0	-35,938,291.0	7,996,902.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2018	350,226,472.0	388,766,316.0	19,401,169.0	140,383,143.0	166,644,184.0	30,567,698.0	-29,764,965.0	-2,875,301.0	7,996,902.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2019	323,002,120.0	382,503,815.0	16,104,763.0	139,440,641.0	167,564,562.0	38,576,653.0	-29,784,299.0	-15,756,026.0	7,996,902.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2020	337,006,267.0	444,437,374.0	7,525,621.0	209,075,927.0	161,150,877.0	82,724,967.0	-36,582,832.0	-22,151,127.0	7,996,902.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2021	437,195,534.0	482,639,565.0	12,927,163.0	269,422,890.0	172,139,303.0	90,847,120.0	-60,145,703.0	-44,284,528.0	7,996,902.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2022	550,477,627.0	621,318,254.0	13,925,086.0	40,168,868.0	180,879,079.0	22,506,395.0	-99,208,603.0	-82,011,534.0	7,996,902.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2023	599,508,761.0	797,362,993.0	-105,769,222.0	584,034,939.0	65,168,612.0	22,528,229.0	-99,258,665.0	-82,058,768.0	7,996,902.0
Nig. Breweries Plc	2024	1,074,881,526.0	1,126,267,553.0	-144,338,449.0	611,057,090.0	465,464,520.0	48,749,913.0	-138,711,297.0	-215,587,225.0	30,983,026.0
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2013	2,516,038.0	2,203,388.0	73,970.0	683,910.0	1,183,938.0	-32,250.0	80,947.0	-162,412.0	63,360.0
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2014	2,569,751.0	3,084,021.0	86,155.0	1,520,725.0	1,241,581.0	-719,515.0	26,592.0	-161,482.0	63,360.0
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2015	2,608,286.0	5,022,544.0	74,357.0	3,405,863.0	1,305,603.0	1,652,580.0	62,000.0	-152,205.0	63,360.0
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2016	2,795,190.0	4,539,683.0	133,475.0	2,833,332.0	1,414,566.0	1,255,425.0	115,424.0	-226,671.0	63,360.0
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2017	2,528,319.0	5,826,562.0	45,058.0	4,113,892.0	1,427,112.0	1,054,611.0	164,956.0	-592,583.0	63,360.0

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Nig. Enamelware Plc	2018	1,650,999.0	4,576,107.0	-3,333.0	2,905,033.0	1,423,779.0	2,697,822.0	81,492.0	-402,774.0	76,032.0
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2019	740,232.0	4,381,630.0	-241,634.0	2,949,496.0	1,182,145.0	520,520.0	0.0	-189,596.0	76,032.0
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2020	497,933.0	4,987,799.0	-350,806.0	3,900,086.0	831,339.0	743,607.0	-68,941.0	-174,272.0	76,032.0
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2021	297,666.0	4,619,354.0	-275,533.0	3,821,038.0	555,806.0	36,918.0	0.0	-36,445.0	76,032.0
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2022	354,804.0	4,408,807.0	-431,224.0	4,035,677.0	144,745.0	-16,507.0	0.0	20,163.0	76,032.0
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2023	227,301.0	6,037,147.0	1,686,057.0	4,109,145.0	1,830,802.0	1,645,184.0	3,058,400.0	0.0	76,032.0
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2024	718,353.0	2,499,514.0	-2,597,798.0	3,155,690.0	-744,354.0	-1,013,516.0	0.0	22,749.0	76,032.0

Source: Financial Statements of Selected Quoted Companies in Nigeria for Various Years

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	REV (₦'000)	TA (₦'000)	PAT (₦'000)	CL (₦'000)	TE (₦'000)	NCFO (₦'000)	NCFI (₦'000)	NCFF (₦'000)	ESO (Unit)
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2013	71,343,088.0	72,296,420.0	5,321,187.0	21,397,087.0	46,436,857.0	9,738,717.0	1,400,485.0	1,989,316.0	3,970,476.0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2014	72,905,679.0	70,965,735.0	5,082,747.0	23,952,048.0	42,538,582.0	7,451,110.0	2,699,576.0	9,145,712.0	3,970,476.0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2015	73,126,070.0	48,106,661.0	2,168,867.0	17,763,887.0	26,584,929.0	3,705,398.0	1,978,982.0	3,941,990.0	3,970,476.0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2016	69,527,537.0	56,261,100.0	389,999.0	18,360,626.0	33,792,289.0	9,331,347.0	3,104,797.0	3,275,295.0	3,970,476.0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2017	54,761,729.0	73,039,610.0	2,235,631.0	35,003,206.0	34,076,230.0	6,576,014.0	4,716,888.0	2,401,225.0	3,970,476.0

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PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	201 8	58,483,0 29.0	74,576,11 9.0	1,630,55 7.0	37,159,7 30.0	33,750,3 79.0	13,245,6 62.0	2,171,01 4.0	- 4.0	- 4.0	3,970,4 76.0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	201 9	47,200,9 19.0	64,315,67 6.0	578,355. 0	26,277,6 64.0	33,816,5 82.0	8,469,68 6.0	931,909. 0	- 0	- 0	3,970,4 76.0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	20 20	38,939,2 23.0	59,486,8 50.0	5,966,99 5.0	28,638,9 42.0	23,896,8 11.0	7,365,76 1.0	489,244. 0	- 0	- 3.0	3,970,4 76.0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	20 21	47,832,5 59.0	69,368,7 07.0	817,322. 0	39,826,7 78.0	23,045,4 66.0	11,456,8 60.0	6,920,41 0.0	- 0.0	- 0	3,970,4 76.0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	20 22	58,264,6 60.0	79,875,53 5.0	1,779,70 4.0	50,611,3 39.0	23,872,1 47.0	3,685,86 3.0	20,423,9 75.0	- 0	- 6.0	3,970,4 76.0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	20 23	67,423,11 1.0	110,826,0 00.0	8,528,4 36.0	82,153,5 32.0	28,677,4 68.0	3,865,67 8.0	3,482,68 4.0	- 0	- 10.0	3,970,4 76.0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	20 24	90,810,4 86.0	118,112,51 7.0	- 45,575,9 43.0	74,387,2 49.0	16,746,6 99.0	58,904,0 35.0	5,040,39 9.0	- 0	- 0	3,970,4 76.0
Unileve r Nig. Plc	201 3	60,004,1 19.0	43,754,11 4.0	4,724,42 9.0	28,072,6 40.0	9,347,92 2.0	11,680,7 45.0	5,858,52 7.0	- 0	- 6.0	3,783,2 98.0
Unileve r Nig. Plc	201 4	55,754,3 09.0	45,736,25 5.0	2,412,34 3.0	31,857,16 4.0	7,478,80 8.0	1,824,79 5.0	3,834,18 3.0	- 0	- 9.0	3,783,2 98.0
Unileve r Nig. Plc	201 5	59,221,74 8.0	50,172,48 4.0	1,192,36 6.0	34,697,6 53.0	8,003,25 3.0	15,589,9 47.0	4,684,54 2.0	- 0	- 4.0	3,783,2 98.0
Unileve r Nig. Plc	201 6	69,777,0 61.0	72,491,30 9.0	3,071,88 5.0	53,513,3 89.0	11,689,9 43.0	5,990,50 6.0	3,883,49 3.0	- 0	- 56.0	3,783,2 98.0
Unileve r Nig. Plc	201 7	85,193,36 9.0	121,084,3 65.0	7,450,0 85.0	36,695,3 07.0	75,908,3 75.0	6,037,79 1.0	3,353,15 3.0	- 0	- 16.0	5,745,0 06.0
Unileve r Nig. Plc	201 8	92,899,9 69.0	131,843,3 73.0	10,552,1 40.0	43,167,0 53.0	82,789,5 43.0	6,943,17 0.0	3,093,50 3.0	- 0	- 2.0	5,745,0 06.0

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Unilever Nig. Plc	2019	60,486,835.0	103,677,519.0	-7,419,674.0	34,808,084.0	66,528,350.0	-11,524,317.0	-4,333,894.0	-5,825,150.0	5,745,006.0
Unilever Nig. Plc	2020	61,959,678.0	91,517,538.0	-3,965,921.0	27,798,857.0	62,129,120.0	-2,401,016.0	-819,984.0	-428,898.0	5,745,006.0
Unilever Nig. Plc	2021	70,523,695.0	108,288,535.0	-3,409,174.0	40,217,689.0	65,761,668.0	-20,089,953.0	-927,920.0	-363,078.0	5,745,006.0
Unilever Nig. Plc	2022	88,570,826.0	125,389,892.0	-4,467,084.0	55,377,157.0	67,564,716.0	-12,031,343.0	-669,429.0	-1,827,837.0	5,745,006.0
Unilever Nig. Plc	2023	103,879,730.0	116,302,344.0	-8,439,895.0	33,797,046.0	74,509,103.0	-3,784,529.0	-1,542,176.0	-8,267,868.0	5,745,006.0
Unilever Nig. Plc	2024	149,522,596.0	141,646,696.0	-15,143,154.0	50,847,675.0	85,106,080.0	-14,547,614.0	-2,618,208.0	-7,178,932.0	5,745,006.0

Source: Financial Statements of Selected Quoted Companies in Nigeria for Various Years

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	REV (₦'000)	TA (₦'000)	PAT (₦'000)	CL (₦'000)	TE (₦'000)	NCFO (₦'000)	NCFI (₦'000)	NCFE (₦'000)	ESO (Unit)
Berger Paints Plc	2013	2,710,986.0	3,627,598.0	257,580.0	798,623.0	2,476,257.0	-165,600.0	-42,717.0	512,599.0	289,824.0
Berger Paints Plc	2014	3,082,930.0	3,640,145.0	148,808.0	816,531.0	2,459,830.0	-462,336.0	-30,573.0	223,590.0	289,824.0
Berger Paints Plc	2015	3,022,264.0	3,895,870.0	330,316.0	1,143,703.0	2,587,330.0	514,780.0	163,177.0	172,740.0	289,824.0
Berger Paints Plc	2016	2,602,824.0	4,102,265.0	224,007.0	1,306,347.0	2,604,181.0	758,941.0	710,249.0	162,484.0	289,824.0
Berger Paints Plc	2017	3,012,648.0	4,311,424.0	246,276.0	1,080,532.0	2,641,145.0	316,725.0	191,106.0	143,179.0	289,824.0

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Berger Paints Plc	2018	3,377,223.0	4,535,299.0	320,509.0	1,285,038.0	2,813,052.0	440,335.0	342,333.0	274,603.0	289,824.0
Berger Paints Plc	2019	3,584,804.0	5,066,449.0	448,733.0	1,488,025.0	3,073,400.0	396,290.0	318,000.0	271,811.0	289,824.0
Berger Paints Plc	2020	3,837,582.0	4,971,872.0	146,028.0	1,328,867.0	3,146,972.0	454,612.0	163,667.0	151,034.0	289,824.0
Berger Paints Plc	2021	4,964,796.0	5,110,669.0	135,635.0	1,439,061.0	3,230,703.0	265,919.0	104,157.0	300,732.0	289,824.0
Berger Paints Plc	2022	6,331,634.0	5,528,528.0	208,670.0	1,690,196.0	3,323,445.0	571,518.0	71,430.0	221,879.0	289,824.0
Berger Paints Plc	2023	7,910,181.0	6,610,970.0	468,797.0	2,056,868.0	3,531,401.0	408,196.0	141,191.0	35,194.0	289,824.0
Berger Paints Plc	2024	10,739,502.0	7,534,781.0	614,960.0	2,835,193.0	3,855,900.0	229,939.0	486,498.0	329,797.0	289,824.0
Beta Glass Plc	2013	14,096,123.0	27,166,481.0	1,473,574.0	9,423,313.0	13,753,157.0	2,922,972.0	1,332,973.0	588,349.0	499,972.0
Beta Glass Plc	2014	16,632,879.0	26,928,387.0	2,390,223.0	7,673,957.0	15,952,981.0	4,341,369.0	1,453,049.0	1,925,533.0	499,972.0
Beta Glass Plc	2015	15,953,224.0	27,171,069.0	1,991,127.0	5,527,007.0	17,578,125.0	4,842,441.0	3,668,180.0	344,143.0	499,972.0
Beta Glass Plc	2016	19,091,192.0	33,184,130.0	3,799,393.0	6,990,457.0	21,474,964.0	4,912,545.0	667,297.0	221,871.0	499,972.0
Beta Glass Plc	2017	22,186,258.0	38,211,613.0	4,115,142.0	9,042,953.0	25,145,114.0	1,076,544.0	2,216,587.0	22,533.0	499,972.0
Beta Glass Plc	2018	26,321,014.0	46,079,629.0	5,052,805.0	13,723,312.0	29,627,573.0	8,614,946.0	6,487,730.0	436,830.0	499,972.0

Jeremiah Patrick EDET, PhD, ACA, Raphael Sunday ETIM, PhD, FCA, FCNA, FCTI and Akpanuko ESSIEN, PhD

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Beta Glass Plc	2019	29,412,252.0	52,080,362.0	5,580,220.0	15,032,650.0	34,558,001.0	5,405,503.0	5,465,631.0	958,503.0	499,972.0
Beta Glass Plc	2020	25,637,010.0	53,963,634.0	3,466,670.0	14,812,299.0	37,189,718.0	3,361,039.0	2,554,948.0	147,350.0	499,972.0
Beta Glass Plc	2021	36,982,815.0	63,112,410.0	5,457,671.0	17,400,029.0	42,127,418.0	7,405,003.0	3,017,141.0	-41,035.0	499,972.0
Beta Glass Plc	2022	54,340,363.0	75,944,552.0	4,685,414.0	26,142,597.0	46,263,350.0	1,312,596.0	4,740,355.0	3,609,199.0	599,966.0
Beta Glass Plc	2023	62,905,451.0	106,851,898.0	6,442,223.0	3,538,605.0	52,005,006.0	11,385,599.0	12,142,676.0	2,954,918.0	599,966.0
Beta Glass Plc	2024	117,580,184.0	137,352,197.0	13,626,830.0	64,940,404.0	64,791,883.0	17,515,552.0	19,937,854.0	13,153,438.0	599,966.0

Source: Financial Statements of Selected Quoted Companies in Nigeria for Various Years

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	REV (N'000)	TA (N'000)	PAT (N'000)	CL (N'000)	TE (N'000)	NCFO (N'000)	NCFI (N'000)	NCFE (N'000)	ESO (Unit)
Champion B. Plc	2013	2,233,259.0	9,137,716.0	1,178,025.0	13,683,275.0	4,608,386.0	1,058,062.0	-933,273.0	0.0	900,000.0
Champion B. Plc	2014	3,302,383.0	9,592,381.0	-754,523.0	3,578,929.0	5,870,431.0	1,008,118.0	-277,159.0	-313,807.0	7,200,000.0
Champion B. Plc	2015	3,501,845.0	10,329,160.0	77,140.0	3,073,998.0	7,121,637.0	1,287,183.0	-653,727.0	0.0	7,829,496.0
Champion B. Plc	2016	3,864,943.0	9,961,240.0	530,389.0	2,208,173.0	7,670,860.0	368,019.0	-418,573.0	0.0	7,829,496.0
Champion B. Plc	2017	4,777,313.0	10,088,861.0	517,562.0	1,627,573.0	8,135,460.0	47,221.0	-855,138.0	0.0	7,829,496.0
Champion B. Plc	2018	4,763,757.0	10,487,010.0	263,807.0	2,305,491.0	7,935,532.0	1,142,454.0	1,267,856.0	0.0	7,829,496.0

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Champion B. Plc	2019	6,927,177.0	10,981,383.0	168,508.0	2,564,456.0	8,031,796.0	1,637,027.0	-1,120,954.0	0.0	7,829,496.0
Champion B. Plc	2020	7,051,806.0	11,368,517.0	158,793.0	2,251,657.0	8,042,994.0	1,976,064.0	-1,620,959.0	-31,826.0	7,829,496.0
Champion B. Plc	2021	10,518,497.0	13,486,815.0	984,233.0	3,435,750.0	9,219,643.0	3,759,396.0	-1,833,581.0	-79,022.0	7,829,496.0
Champion B. Plc	2022	12,288,893.0	15,453,585.0	1,585,978.0	2,926,961.0	11,119,384.0	2,260,174.0	-2,851,121.0	-92,272.0	7,829,496.0
Champion B. Plc	2023	12,704,274.0	20,533,079.0	370,563.0	7,968,406.0	11,195,299.0	5,822,757.0	-6,581,822.0	1,014,875.0	7,829,496.0
Champion B. Plc	2024	20,890,735.0	21,345,197.0	816,995.0	9,217,856.0	12,056,086.0	5,183,808.0	-808,846.0	-2,509,526.0	8,947,996.0
BUA Cement Plc	2013	15,311,004.0	15,058,476.0	1,559,031.0	4,101,944.0	8,284,619.0	2,071,903.0	-1,157,105.0	-439,656.0	1,256,678.0
BUA Cement Plc	2014	15,119,051.0	15,780,013.0	1,918,362.0	3,496,155.0	9,445,658.0	1,863,994.0	-1,786,509.0	-258,179.0	1,256,678.0
BUA Cement Plc	2015	13,037,847.0	17,146,883.0	1,201,108.0	4,145,323.0	10,144,768.0	2,569,229.0	-2,260,421.0	223,636.0	1,256,678.0
BUA Cement Plc	2016	14,087,553.0	20,030,222.0	1,253,805.0	5,501,981.0	11,493,272.0	2,799,490.0	-980,194.0	-360,490.0	1,256,678.0
BUA Cement Plc	2017	19,588,261.0	24,648,676.0	3,223,854.0	7,165,954.0	14,412,207.0	3,625,888.0	-2,571,250.0	-384,459.0	1,256,678.0
BUA Cement Plc	2018	31,721,962.0	347,746,456.0	5,731,321.0	11,554,244.0	333,487,688.0	1,362,117.0	-2,733,048.0	-166,894.0	13,143,502.0
BUA Cement Plc	2019	32,148,368.0	356,753,843.0	7,283,413.0	13,448,729.0	340,771,502.0	10,964,758.0	-6,717,917.0	-204,265.0	13,143,502.0
BUA Cement Plc	2020	209,443,487.0	766,302,578.0	72,344,336.0	208,100,189.0	375,954,728.0	65,112,598.0	-128,849,627.0	1,728,508,889.0	33,864,354.0

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BUA Cement Plc	2021	257,327,091.0	728,507,473.0	90,079,011.0	145,355,120.0	398,116,748.0	198,957,257.0	-58,076,721.0	-214,503,647.0	33,864,354.0
BUA Cement Plc	2022	360,989,105.0	874,011,884.0	101,010,626.0	25,756,156.0	411,112,542.0	149,573,594.0	-102,275,234.0	-61,628,432.0	33,864,354.0
BUA Cement Plc	2023	459,998,999.0	1,215,686,377.0	69,454,750.0	377,037,627.0	385,224,150.0	150,052,489.0	-104,119,517.0	8,005,350.0	33,864,354.0
BUA Cement Plc	2024	876,469,849.0	1,570,351,865.0	73,909,235.0	574,554,529.0	388,548,235.0	405,253,085.0	-272,678,983.0	-370,993,558.0	33,864,354.0

Source: Financial Statements of Selected Quoted Companies in Nigeria for Various Years

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	REV (₦'000)	TA (₦'000)	PAT (₦'000)	CL (₦'000)	TE (₦'000)	NCFO (₦'000)	NCFI (₦'000)	NCFE (₦'000)	ESO (Unit)
Cutix Plc	2013	1,929,477.0	1,073,865.0	151,423.0	399,744.0	597,554.0	193,539.0	-67,922.0	105,291.0	880,662.0
Cutix Plc	2014	2,234,959.0	1,744,670.0	207,116.0	696,154.0	699,703.0	126,655.0	504,907.0	156,882.0	880,662.0
Cutix Plc	2015	2,358,412.0	1,968,813.0	149,209.0	922,892.0	743,711.0	222,355.0	217,408.0	-17,784.0	880,662.0
Cutix Plc	2016	2,835,862.0	1,891,720.0	190,551.0	756,297.0	870,217.0	644,996.0	-24,045.0	563,973.0	880,662.0
Cutix Plc	2017	3,675,712.0	2,329,792.0	257,497.0	1,112,406.0	1,013,969.0	190,068.0	-45,474.0	108,335.0	880,662.0
Cutix Plc	2018	5,057,374.0	2,836,262.0	440,295.0	1,359,513.0	1,299,292.0	609,478.0	227,573.0	393,031.0	880,662.0
Cutix Plc	2019	5,434,107.0	2,861,339.0	477,070.0	1,032,494.0	1,613,091.0	427,399.0	197,527.0	221,616.0	3,522,644.0
Cutix Plc	2020	5,025,500.0	3,627,990.0	393,053.0	1,313,836.0	1,805,638.0	90,130.0	100,166.0	65,044.0	3,522,644.0
Cutix Plc	2021	6,745,521.0	4,801,452.0	601,627.0	2,308,511.0	2,214,333.0	295,955.0	429,239.0	74,282.0	3,522,644.0
Cutix Plc	2022	7,852,391.0	5,086,471.0	790,467.0	2,109,127.0	2,767,160.0	1,203,416.0	248,645.0	942,769.0	3,522,644.0
Cutix Plc	2023	9,225,071.0	5,796,790.0	792,132.0	2,332,152.0	3,232,801.0	514,849.0	263,253.0	258,985.0	3,522,644.0

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Cutix Plc	2024	12,167,838.0	7,212,949.0	1,075,397.0	2,667,419.0	3,880,083.0	985,994.0	-396,790.0	-466,447.0	3,522,644.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2013	371,551,567.0	821,699,780.0	210,262,754.0	150,992,846.0	571,562,826.0	275,953,727.0	-168,619,000.0	-81,589,914.0	17,040,508.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2014	371,534,117.0	963,441,064.0	185,814,123.0	205,829,677.0	638,543,114.0	195,608,275.0	-162,125,000.0	-84,576,991.0	17,040,508.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2015	389,215,000.0	1,124,475,000.0	213,171,000.0	140,586,000.0	748,479,000.0	249,235,000.0	-131,571,000.0	-116,052,000.0	17,040,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2016	426,129,000.0	1,502,564,000.0	368,205,000.0	390,226,000.0	981,367,000.0	236,064,000.0	-75,879,000.0	-112,637,000.0	17,040,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2017	552,364,000.0	1,611,087,000.0	254,630,000.0	343,956,000.0	991,017,000.0	297,968,000.0	-51,278,000.0	-209,732,000.0	17,040,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2018	618,301,000.0	1,721,974,000.0	481,456,000.0	284,759,000.0	1,293,548,000.0	337,186,000.0	-94,146,000.0	-236,528,000.0	17,040,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2019	610,247,000.0	1,823,984,000.0	261,349,000.0	410,575,000.0	1,282,249,000.0	333,484,000.0	-124,219,000.0	-262,458,000.0	17,040,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2020	719,945,000.0	2,116,060,000.0	352,609,000.0	538,613,000.0	1,352,377,000.0	398,290,000.0	-199,335,000.0	-185,894,000.0	17,040,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2021	993,399,000.0	2,582,298,000.0	381,100,000.0	837,858,000.0	1,461,472,000.0	595,746,000.0	-170,226,770.0	-290,558,000.0	17,040,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2022	1,205,401,000.0	2,658,463,000.0	402,857,000.0	775,840,000.0	1,491,535,000.0	364,185,000.0	-118,485,000.0	-380,581,000.0	17,040,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2023	1,297,639,000.0	3,070,468,000.0	490,323,000.0	1,127,236,000.0	1,602,964,000.0	406,759,000.0	-83,782,000.0	-336,517,000.0	17,040,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2024	2,192,695,000.0	5,194,814,000.0	1,027,217,000.0	1,746,596,000.0	2,127,616,000.0	653,366,000.0	-830,938,000.0	-223,683,000.0	16,874,000.0

Source: Financial Statements of Selected Quoted Companies in Nigeria for Various Years

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

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Company	Year	REV (₦'000)	TA (₦'000)	PAT (₦'000)	CL (₦'000)	TE (₦'000)	NCFO (₦'000)	NCFI (₦'000)	NCFE (₦'000)	ESO (Unit)
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2013	102,467,361.0	87,112,182.0	13,537,612.0	26,246,090.0	57,125,832.0	-	-	-	12,000,000.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2014	94,103,677.0	97,287,804.0	11,908,690.0	33,220,434.0	51,413,720.0	-	-	-	12,000,000.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2015	100,092,221.0	97,287,804.0	12,659,855.0	34,532,088.0	58,526,202.0	-	-	-	12,000,000.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2016	167,409,161.0	106,671,333.0	14,198,693.0	35,516,958.0	66,388,057.0	-	-	-	12,000,000.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2017	198,120,639.0	198,064,664.0	37,822,609.0	91,644,487.0	99,207,358.0	-	-	-	12,000,000.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2018	146,549,176.0	178,523,711.0	25,830,941.0	66,033,588.0	107,180,126.0	-	-	-	12,000,000.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2019	78,608,142.0	174,646,907.0	12,869,456.0	62,487,298.0	106,849,582.0	-	-	-	12,000,000.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2020	206,360,656.0	259,280,544.0	31,370,659.0	122,752,272.0	125,302,902.0	-	-	-	12,146,878.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2021	276,054,781.0	349,382,869.0	22,660,116.0	207,221,431.0	129,830,169.0	-	-	-	12,146,878.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2022	403,245,988.0	490,969,836.0	54,346,390.0	305,170,514.0	172,029,685.0	-	-	-	12,146,878.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2023	441,452,953.0	601,040,524.0	71,999,460.0	518,900,557.0	81,809,910.0	-	-	-	12,146,878.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2024	665,689,763.0	1,018,344,271.0	190,866,449.0	798,723,006.0	179,695,466.0	-	-	-	12,146,878.0

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Lafarge Africa Plc	2013	97,174,505.0	159,866,917.0	28,022,200.0	39,334,496.0	92,641,665.0	35,452,200.0	-1,235,097.0	-22,837,480.0	3,001,600.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2014	105,848,657.0	343,627,558.0	28,360,146.0	36,526,476.0	276,664,338.0	37,737,758.0	-33,050,495.0	-23,249,783.0	4,404,176.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2015	114,558,245.0	381,272,953.0	29,837,395.0	47,557,407.0	302,601,869.0	33,733,822.0	2,093,919.0	-33,412,891.0	4,554,902.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2016	87,198,416.0	537,598,212.0	20,778,348.0	112,592,247.0	340,094,143.0	-30,907,024.0	5,048,387.0	13,459,929.0	5,480,734.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2017	177,170,362.0	616,169,940.0	-13,223,626.0	282,455,768.0	264,768,895.0	1,778,571.0	-6,706,392.0	20,729,761.0	5,575,776.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2018	187,043,475.0	577,692,296.0	4,141,764.0	173,870,677.0	255,743,725.0	39,125,112.0	11,801,206.0	40,615,290.0	8,673,430.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2019	188,407,004.0	500,081,653.0	22,721,616.0	89,216,038.0	361,421,559.0	77,275,692.0	-5,918,974.0	-39,659,029.0	16,107,798.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2020	202,530,359.0	505,332,716.0	28,714,884.0	124,522,776.0	373,974,933.0	48,655,540.0	6,542,358.0	-27,528,292.0	16,107,798.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2021	262,299,071.0	534,054,123.0	53,455,912.0	133,856,097.0	395,349,470.0	-748,175,715.0	-12,487,697.0	-59,073,388.0	16,107,798.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2022	340,633,999.0	609,182,343.0	55,032,460.0	169,932,087.0	434,275,803.0	-91,308,889.0	-19,890,609.0	-10,792,645.0	16,107,798.0

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Africa Plc											
Lafarge Africa Plc	2023	372,513,521.0	689,780,550.0	48,056,437.0	2,122,659,591.0	450,120,336.0	147,011,474.0	-32,680,014.0	-63,818,929.0	16,107,798.0	
Lafarge Africa Plc	2024	651,024,707.0	997,632,873.0	99,687,811.0	411,175.322.0	519,251,658.0	200,924,994.0	-61,560,354.0	-72,445.537.0	16,107,798.0	

Source: Financial Statements of Selected Quoted Companies in Nigeria for Various Years

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	REV (₦'000)	TA (₦'000)	PAT (₦'000)	CL (₦'000)	TE (₦'000)	NCFO (₦'000)	NCFI (₦'000)	NCFE (₦'000)	ESO (Unit)
Meyer Paints Plc	2013	1,500,112.0	2,597,517.0	-26,149.0	750,754.0	622,382.0	246,381.0	21,541.0	-209,268.0	325,000.0
Meyer Paints Plc	2014	1,340,104.0	2,435,368.0	-33,106.0	690,701.0	581,626.0	140,348.0	-16,849.0	-213,494.0	325,000.0
Meyer Paints Plc	2015	1,187,236.0	2,301,121.0	73,230.0	594,689.0	638,100.0	11,864.0	101.0	-110,431.0	291,490.0
Meyer Paints Plc	2016	1,091,000.0	2,178,705.0	214,402.0	784,368.0	423,698.0	-36,215.0	3,291.0	1,196.0	291,490.0
Meyer Paints Plc	2017	1,097,061.0	1,890,966.0	267,739.0	1,273,952.0	302,969.0	20,822.0	24,054.0	58,593.0	497,728.0
Meyer Paints Plc	2018	970,134.0	1,839,132.0	319,297.0	1,053,881.0	621,063.0	28,336.0	-1,831.0	-21,642.0	497,728.0
Meyer Paints Plc	2019	1,106,116.0	3,720,214.0	-13,493.0	2,964,620.0	607,570.0	1,949,902.0	131,402.0	361,214.0	497,728.0
Meyer Paints Plc	2020	827,599.0	2,952,080.0	1,108,506.0	1,272,315.0	1,716,076.0	2,341,267.0	3,240,078.0	10,047.0	497,728.0

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Meyer Paints Plc	2021	1,118,098.0	1,986,513.0	33,673.0	956,666.0	1,003,158.0	-310,230.0	79,002.0	-762,108.0	497,728.0
Meyer Paints Plc	2022	1,435,032.0	1,907,674.0	393,617.0	468,779.0	1,396,775.0	-153,867.0	73,173.0	11,484.0	497,728.0
Meyer Paints Plc	2023	2,266,791.0	2,424,767.0	235,969.0	756,395.0	1,632,744.0	105,719.0	89,675.0	-166.0	497,728.0
Meyer Paints Plc	2024	3,123,957.0	2,813,107.0	295,406.0	988,432.0	1,778,800.0	30,653.0	194,453.0	170,228.0	497,728.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2013	15,519,856.0	9,376,225.0	562,350.0	5,212,095.0	3,267,313.0	1,289,816.0	373,437.0	678,657.0	409,500.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2014	15,519,856.0	11,032,131.0	394,690.0	6,664,532.0	3,747,004.0	1,635,578.0	123,294.0	1,202,695.0	409,500.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2015	15,155,102.0	11,734,739.0	196,640.0	6,756,676.0	3,802,832.0	494,129.0	442,487.0	387,001.0	982,800.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2016	12,189,558.0	13,098,732.0	412,386.0	7,770,121.0	4,375,223.0	1,557,076.0	364,785.0	1,500,767.0	1,042,070.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2017	15,921,022.0	12,974,483.0	190,540.0	7,622,014.0	4,463,206.0	2,090,468.0	62,005.0	1,925,303.0	1,042,070.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2018	17,612,291.0	15,156,727.0	486,120.0	7,884,358.0	4,822,994.0	167,810.0	-60,195.0	1,512,711.0	1,042,070.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2019	20,330,040.0	12,358,342.0	1,574,909.0	4,462,649.0	5,932,044.0	4,837,585.0	138,815.0	3,910,336.0	1,250,844.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2020	21,521,097.0	19,802,249.0	3,456,694.0	7,654,807.0	8,687,013.0	4,806,873.0	786,167.0	1,678,498.0	1,250,844.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2021	32,007,979.0	29,693,840.0	4,384,859.0	15,235,021.0	12,401,122.0	202,869.0	514,462.0	4,029,988.0	1,250,844.0

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Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2022	42,128,595.0	36,913,111.0	4,411,111.0	20,213,120.0	15,013,073.0	434,146.0	255,479.0	307,953.0	1,250,844.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2023	47,723,375.0	46,673,301.0	3,418,992.0	29,080,166.0	16,178,032.0	1,793,499.0	-175,266.0	4,599,872.0	1,250,844.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2024	73,492,246.0	45,907,461.0	906,511.0	18,701,228.0	21,624,873.0	1,635,176.0	646,461.0	17,945.376.0	1,250,844.0

Source: Financial Statements of Selected Quoted Companies in Nigeria for Various Years

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	REV (₦'000)	TA (₦'000)	PAT (₦'000)	CL (₦'000)	TE (₦'000)	NCFO (₦'000)	NCFI (₦'000)	NCFF (₦'000)	ESO (Unit)
CAP Plc	2013	6,195,824.0	3,035,012.0	1,416,795.0	1,684,573.0	1,268,148.0	1,448,652.0	18,245.0	-1,276,649.0	700,000.0
CAP Plc	2014	6,987,604.0	3,080,882.0	1,662,426.0	1,825,999.0	1,180,573.0	1,340,956.0	42,304.0	-1,749,978.0	700,000.0
CAP Plc	2015	7,056,876.0	3,409,300.0	1,739,559.0	1,833,838.0	1,520,133.0	261,700.0	138,767.0	-1,027,010.0	700,000.0
CAP Plc	2016	6,813,984.0	4,915,999.0	1,603,357.0	2,495,428.0	2,283,490.0	134,054.0	-60,724.0	-475,653.0	700,000.0
CAP Plc	2017	7,113,950.0	5,013,990.0	1,498,730.0	2,671,721.0	2,242,220.0	1,804,682.0	40,935.0	-1,356,969.0	700,000.0
CAP Plc	2018	7,670,315.0	6,311,246.0	2,029,343.0	3,375,254.0	2,808,939.0	1,742,787.0	163,111.0	-1,930,995.0	700,000.0
CAP Plc	2019	8,410,650.0	6,760,961.0	1,742,088.0	4,069,187.0	2,521,684.0	1,753,000.0	152,893.0	-1,930,995.0	700,000.0
CAP Plc	2020	8,876,191.0	8,526,076.0	1,223,124.0	4,781,268.0	3,744,808.0	990,962.0	137,226.0	322,892.0	700,000.0
CAP Plc	2021	14,207,818.0	12,115,919.0	1,122,583.0	7,532,448.0	4,409,788.0	-1,278,694.0	-395,375.0	-1,502,309.0	788,260.0
CAP Plc	2022	19,208,470.0	13,406,204.0	2,376,208.0	6,470,057.0	6,599,601.0	1,340,259.0	-540,163.0	388,990.0	814,748.0

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CAP Plc	2023	23,890,279.0	15,373,521.0	2,514,737.0	6,906,761.0	7,969,707.0	3,581,356.0	327,636.0	-	2,018,374.0	814,748.0
CAP Plc	2024	36,362,182.0	19,677,179.0	3,807,258.0	7,910,709.0	10,636,487.0	5,034,673.0	1,605,723.0	-	1,410,640.0	814,748.0

Source: Financial Statements of Selected Quoted Companies in Nigeria for Various Years

APPENDIX THREE (iii)

Average of Raw Data for Twenty-three (23) Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria from 2013 to 2024

Company	Year	REV (N'000)	TA (N'000)	PAT (N'000)	SP (N)	TE (N'000)	NCFO (N'000)	NCFI (N'000)	NCFE (N'000)	ESO (Unit)	NCF (N'000)
Manufacturing	2013	71,119,216.0	95,545,293.5	15,190,085.6	104.0	52,533,681.4	21,201,276.1	11,697,533.7	7,429,719.9	3,239,936.9	2,074,022.5
Manufacturing	2014	72,099,141.7	110,390,654.7	13,990,515.9	85.3	66,667,136.8	16,275,947.9	11,888,790.0	10,373,122.2	3,576,210.8	5,985,964.3
Manufacturing	2015	74,686,292.0	119,958,493.8	14,932,075.4	74.0	69,121,556.8	21,555,290.8	9,696,140.5	12,146,692.3	3,679,619.6	287,542.0
Manufacturing	2016	80,622,622.7	149,624,855.0	20,314,513.0	64.0	81,287,526.4	18,925,673.9	4,346,966.6	5,960,186.0	3,674,308.0	8,618,521.3
Manufacturing	2017	104,775,444.2	180,540,381.1	16,772,845.2	101.1	87,023,342.4	21,553,739.8	9,248,694.2	10,944,875.8	3,980,115.0	1,360,169.8
Manufacturing	2018	113,390,789.8	202,172,509.4	27,268,696.6	94.9	118,051,289.7	21,247,013.7	8,785,516.0	12,427,804.1	4,726,105.7	33,693.5
Manufacturing	2019	107,804,784.7	206,413,674.3	16,037,822.7	84.6	120,878,527.6	25,090,226.1	10,780,548.9	16,121,847.3	5,173,285.0	1,812,170.1
Manufacturing	2020	127,187,095.4	246,005,861.4	23,276,330.3	91.5	131,593,953.4	41,088,815.7	19,961,872.1	59,450,086.3	6,874,760.5	80,577,029.9
Manufacturing	2021	168,513,362.6	285,145,940.3	27,187,761.6	95.1	139,162,946.0	21,076,326.7	19,818,877.8	25,809,256.6	6,878,597.9	24,551,807.7
Manufacturing	2022	222,708,034.6	326,037,477.1	31,192,399.2	73.9	146,599,591.9	28,072,132.3	19,153,826.3	14,639,995.3	6,884,097.1	5,721,689.3

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Manufac turing	20 23	252,080, 101.4	410,024, 673.2	13,704,1 57.0	111. 0	136,712, 095.9	41,380, 735.1	- 13,256, 773.8	- 12,495, 603.0	6,884, 097.1	15,628, 358.3
Manufac turing	20 24	414,401, 570.4	590,673, 696.3	22,631, 205.6	89. 9	195,491, 419.1	60,685, 632.0	- 65,111,2 49.3	- 26,099, 989.1	8,190,6 57.0	- 30,525, 606.5

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2025)

APPENDIX FOUR (iv)

Graphical Illustration of Accounting Data of Quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria from 2013 to 2024

Source: Researcher’s Illustration (2025)

Source: Researcher’s Illustration (2025)

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